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Short Description:

The overall objective of DISMAR has been to develop an advanced information system for monitoring and forecasting the marine environment to improve management of pollution crises in coastal and ocean regions of Europe. The DISMAR services are made in support of public administrations and emergency services responsible for prevention, mitigation and recovery of crises such as oil spill pollution and harmful algae blooms (HABs). In the first two years of the project, we developed the first version of a prototype information system, DISPRO-1. The design and implementation of this prototype was based on user requirements extracted from a survey of existing monitoring services in the participating countries (Norway, Germany, Italy, France, UK and Ireland), complemented with a literature review of recent coastal zone GIS for environmental monitoring, forecasting and risk management. The implementation was based on state-of-the-art GIS and web technologies, in line with recommendations from INSPIRE and GMES. In the third and final year of the project, an extended version – DISPRO-2 – was implemented, tested and validated.

A number of algorithms and models for generation of products for marine pollution monitoring and forecasting were used or developed during the project. These products, algorithms and models include:

- Ground based radar Doppler (for pollution detection and guiding skimming ships),
- ENVISAT ASAR (for oil pollution detection, using both single and multi-channel data),
- Aircraft data (IR/UV, laser fluorosensor, microwave sensors, fused for oil spill detection),
- New Ferrybox sensor (for *in-situ* water quality survey and satellite validation).
- ENVISAT MERIS/AATSR (for water quality and algae blooms survey),
- AVHRR for monitoring of sea-surface temperature,
- SeaWiFS, Aqua-MODIS and Terra-MODIS (for water quality and algae blooms survey),
- A 3D oil spill drift model (OD3D) that can be set up for multiple ocean areas,
- An oil spill drift model tailored for the Adriatic Sea,
- An ecological model (for prognostic information on algal blooms, set up for the western English Channel).

The report describes each of the developed products, along with the algorithm or model generating it.

In parallel with product development, DISPRO was developed based on the OGC WMS specification, and other standard web technologies and tools, including JavaScript, CSS, Cocoon and eXist. Developing a web-based GIS with multiple data providers required harmonisation of data and metadata to facilitate access to distributed heterogeneous repositories. Data harmonisation, i.e. the process of making multi-source data and product repositories interoperable, was thus closely linked to the DISPRO development. Harmonisation also involves making metadata interoperable, both discovery metadata (i.e. metadata used by DISPRO to locate and download products) and technical metadata (i.e. metadata needed by the prototype to be able to manipulate a product, e.g. overlay it correctly on a map or another product). A DISPRO metadata schema was developed as a profile of the ISO 19115 standard, incorporating the Core Metadata element set. The metadata schema was encoded in a new

XML Schema, also developed in the project, as the forthcoming ISO encoding of ISO 19115, ISO 19139, was not available.

In the first demonstration phase (DEMO-1), user testing and validation of DISPRO-1 were conducted in an informal manner through meetings and discussions with end-users and within the partner organisations. However, a more formal approach was developed during this phase, based on best practices for user testing and validation and incorporating methodologies from earlier EC projects. The formal approach was used in the second demonstration phase (DEMO-2), and the main findings are reported, along with concrete recommendations for functionality needed in a future GMES service for oil spill and algal bloom monitoring and forecasting. The main features requested were:

- Support for handling of time series, like model forecasts and series of satellite images
- Improved organisation of menus and layer lists, making it easier to find relevant layers
- Consistent naming of layer groups and individual layers, across all regions
- More information on the layers displayed, e.g. the colour coding and symbols used
- Enhanced capabilities for overlaying multiple raster layers, and for changing contrast/colours
- Increase access to data in near-real-time, and include more data providers
- Further downloading and export capabilities
- More support information, e.g. regulations and emergency plans, online help

From a service development point of view, we recommend building on the standards, technologies and tools used in DISMAR. The strengths of using DISPRO as a basis for future GMES services lie in its adherence to de facto standards for data and metadata distribution. The availability of free software for setting up data servers (a.k.a. DISPRO nodes) also makes it an attractive choice. The easy-to-use interface, accessible in any browser, is a compelling reason for users wanting access to GMES products and services.

On the whole, both providers and end-users have overall positive experiences with the development and validation of DISPRO. The major benefit for providers is that they can retain their processing chain, including any legacy systems, up to the point of data/metadata delivery, and need only develop format transformation routines if their original formats are different from those supported by their OGC WMS server of choice. Public domain software is available for setting up a DISPRO node, i.e., a WMS server. Several web-based commercial GIS also supports the WMS specification, so providers that have purchased a COTS GIS can also use this to make their products available through the DISPRO system. The major benefit for the users is that they need no special software to access the system; a common web browser will do. Another benefit is that DISPRO also offers the opportunity of downloading data sets, through a web-based link in the metadata specification.

Partners owning: all (all partners are listed in Appendix B)

Partners contributed: All

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of DISMAR has been to develop an advanced information system for monitoring and forecasting the marine environment to improve management of pollution crises in coastal and ocean regions of Europe. The DISMAR services are made in support of public administrations and emergency services responsible for prevention, mitigation and recovery of crises such as oil spill pollution and harmful algae blooms (HABs).

To meet this objective, the main activities of the project have been focused on:

- Development of products, algorithms and models for marine pollution monitoring and forecasting within the two application areas (oil spills and HABs). This work has included analysis of both single and multi-source data (Chapters 3 and 7).
- Development of the prototype service, DISPRO, including all activities from the initial requirements capture and analysis leading to the system design (Chapter 2), metadata and data harmonisation (Chapter 4), and the implementation of DISPRO based on de facto web-GIS standards, technologies and tools (Chapter 5).
- Demonstration and validation of DISPRO in five European ocean and coastal zone areas, involving key users in public administration and authorities, national operational pollution monitoring agencies, and regional agencies such as the EEA (Chapter 6). Closely linked to this activity, are the dissemination activities aiming at making results known to a wide user community (Chapter 8), and the assessment conducted by independent experts in the targeted applications domains, GMES and web services in general (Chapter 9).

In the first two years of the project, we developed the first version of the prototype information system, DISPRO-1. The design and implementation of this prototype was based on user requirements extracted from a survey of existing monitoring services in the participating countries (Norway, Germany, Italy, France, UK and Ireland), complemented with a literature review of recent coastal zone GIS for environmental monitoring, forecasting and risk management. The implementation was based on state-of-the-art GIS and web technologies, in line with recommendations from INSPIRE and GMES. In the third and final year of the project, an extended version – DISPRO-2 – was implemented, tested and validated.

Chapter 10 summarises the overall conclusions from the project and make recommendations for future development of GMES services, based on our experiences, users' and experts' feedback.

2 Requirements analysis and prototype design

In the beginning of the project we conducted a survey of user requirements by reviewing the existing processing chains of national pollution monitoring services in the targeted ocean and coastal zone areas of Europe. This enabled us to understand the current capabilities and shortcomings of the data sources, analysis, prediction and visualisation tools, as well as the underlying infrastructure set up to handle the data and information used in (pre-)operational pollution monitoring. The objectives were twofold: (1) identify requirements for integration of different observational data and models for use in marine monitoring and forecasting, and (2) clarify technical requirements such as data formats, types and volumes of data that must be handled by a future service with distributed data providers and users accessing the service via Internet.

Based on the requirements analysis, testing of available technologies and tools, and drawing on experience from other, related projects, we designed the initial DISPRO architecture.

2.1 User requirements

The initial user requirements capture and analysis activity established the category of service needed in each area, i.e. oil spill and/or HAB monitoring, data sources used and the information needed by the users. Table 2-1 summarises these findings. As the development of DISPRO progressed, these requirements were elaborated and revised, as users requested enhanced or new functionality and/or improved information products.

Table 2-1 High-level user requirements for pollution monitoring services.

Area / Service	Data sources used	Information needed
North Sea/ Skagerrak: Oil Spill Monitoring	Satellite SAR images. Meteorological data (wind, currents). Oil spill drift model. Background data (coastline, location of platforms, etc.).	Position of the potential spill. Date and time of observation. Estimated size of polluted area. Wind speed and direction. Polluter category (e.g. platform). Name of polluter (if available). Probability level (high, medium, low).
North Sea/ Skagerrak: Algae Monitoring	Satellite data (MERIS, MODIS, SeaWiFS, SAR). Ships of opportunity Ferrybox systems. Ferrybox water samples. Airborne SLAR. Meteorological data (wind, currents). Ecological model.	Chlorophyll-a concentration. Algae species information. Wind and currents (speed and direction). Expert's analysis of current algae situation. Predicted evolution and spread of a potential HAB.
Coast of Germany: Oil Spill Monitoring	Aircraft data (SLAR, IR/UV, IALFS, MWR). Satellite SAR images. Meteorological data (wind, currents). Background data (coastline, location of platforms, ship routes, etc.).	Amount, extent and type of spill. Estimate of oil thickness. Meteorological and sea state conditions.
Coast of Germany: Algae Monitoring	Aircraft data (SLAR, IR/UV, IALFS, MWR). Satellite data (MERIS, SeaWiFS). Meteorological data (wind, currents).	Amount, extent and type of bloom. Distribution of Gelbstoff, location of fronts, chlorophyll fluorescence. Meteorological conditions.
Coast of Italy: Oil Spill Monitoring	Satellite SAR images. Meteorological data (wind, currents). Oil spill drift model. Background data (coastline, known ship routes, etc.).	Position of the potential spill. Date and time of observation. Length, width and perimeter of spill. Probability level (percentage).
Coast of Italy: Algae Monitoring	Satellite data (MERIS, MODIS, TM/ETM, AVHRR). Meteorological data (wind, currents).	Location, extent and type of bloom (e.g. mucilage, "red tides"). Meteorological conditions. Sea surface temperature. Forecast of spread.
Coast of France: Oil Spill Monitoring	Satellite SAR images. Meteorological data (wind, currents). Oil spill drift model. Background data (coastline, known ship routes, etc.).	Pollution report (POLREP) with identification of a potential spill and its source (if possible), formatted according to the agreement of Bonn.
Western English Channel: Algae Monitoring	Satellite data (MERIS, MODIS, SeaWiFS, AVHRR). Meteorological data (wind, currents).	Chlorophyll-a concentration. Underwater visibility. Suspended particulate matter concentration. Coloured dissolved organic material.

2.2 Technical requirements

The INSPIRE Architecture and Standards Position Paper [S02] and Reference Data and Metadata Position Paper [RBPH02] documents were used as overall guidelines for a reference architecture and selection of standards for geo-spatial data and metadata, and web-GIS and web services in general. In addition, we consulted recent and ongoing RTD projects within the field of marine pollution and/or environmental web services, such as SODA, TEASE, RAMSES and OCEANIDES, to draw upon their expertise and experiences.

The identification of specific ISO, OGC and W3C standards as the foundation of DISPRO, led to an in-depth investigation of key standards and available tools implementing them. Chapter 4 presents highlights of the review of metadata and data standards, the metadata schema developed in the project, and the formats used in DISPRO. The major software tools reviewed in the beginning of the project are presented in Table 2-2. In addition, tools for creating, retrieval, updating and deletion of XML files were tested and evaluated. Chapter 5 provides more information about the selected tools and how they were used in the implementation of DISPRO.

Table 2-2 Open-source geo-processing software.

Tool / Reference	Description
University of Minnesota MapServer (http://mapserver.gis.umn.edu/)	MapServer is a development environment for building spatially enabled Internet applications. It supports a variety of standard vector and raster formats, can be integrated with the PostgreSQL/Postgis spatially enabled database, and is OpenGIS WMS (web map server) compliant.
PostgreSQL (http://postgresql.org)	PostgreSQL is an advanced open-source object-relational database management system. It supports almost all SQL constructs, including subselects, transactions, and user-defined types and functions.
Postgis (http://postgis.refrains.net/)	PostGIS adds support for geographic objects to the PostgreSQL. It spatially enables the PostgreSQL server allowing it to be used as a backend spatial database for GIS. PostGIS conforms to the OpenGIS "Simple Features Specification for SQL".
GeoServer (http://docs.codehaus.org/display/GEOS/Home)	The GeoServer project is a Java (J2EE) implementation of the OpenGIS Consortium's WFS (Web Feature Server) specification. It also supports WMS. GeoServer is built on GeoTools.
GeoClient (http://docs.codehaus.org/display/GEOS/Home)	Part of the GeoServer suite, GeoClient is a graphical Web Feature Server client, written in Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG) and ECMAScript/JavaScript.
GeoTools (http://geotools.org)	GeoTools is a Java library for manipulating and displaying geographic maps.
GISToolkit (http://gistoolkit.sourceforge.net/)	The GISToolkit is a free java based mapping toolkit. it has the ability to read geographical data from a variety of data sources and display this information to the user.

2.3 Prototype architecture

Based on the review and analysis of user requirements, standards and open-source tools, we defined a multi-tier distributed architecture for DISPRO:

- Tier 1: Viewer Client
- Tier 2: WMS (Web Map Service) Client + Intermediary applications (e.g. map layer aggregator, metadata browser).
- Tier 3: WMS (Web Map Service) Servers + Other geo-spatial services (e.g. OGC catalogue servers, met-ocean or ecological model services).
- Tier 4: Databases.

The main advantage of this design is that it allows for substitution of sub-systems within each layer, as long as they comply to the chosen protocol of communication: HTTP between tier 1 and tier 2, WMS between tier 2 and 3, and WMS between tier 3 and 4. If other services are included in tier 3, they can use another OGC protocol for communication to catalogue databases, or a legacy system protocol for communicating with databases containing model results.

3 Product, algorithm and model development

3.1 Ground based radar for observation of biogenic slicks

3.1.1 Introduction

The survey on oil pollution of a limited area by means of stationary (coast based) radar was tested at the two test sites at the German coast. To extend the surveyed areas tests with ship-based systems were conducted in addition. The first two years the developments were concentrated on the acquisition and interpretation maps of the radar cross-section. Radar images series acquired every hour were analysed to detect the change in the small-scale roughness of the sea surface as it is induced by different processes i.e. by biogenic slicks, current - current interactions or current interaction with the bottom topography. By using these features the tests became independent from real oil spill pollution and could be conducted during periods of our own choice. For the DISMAR demonstrations a Web Map Server for the German node was set up and maintained during the project's runtime.

3.1.2 Methods

Sea surface roughness patterns were observed with land- or ship-based X-band radar. The spatial resolution of the radar images was 7.5 m. The main sources of spatio-temporal fluctuation of the radar backscatter are speckle noise and a periodic variation of the bottom signature due to the tidal cycle. Three techniques to separate the spatial changes were tested and their results were presented in the DISMAR reports (see e.g. [Z+04]). The tested algorithms were: (1) temporal averaging of the image sequences, (2) calculation of the dominant Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) from the averaged images of a tidal cycle, and (3) the optical flow (spatial shift) from the dominant EOFs of different tidal cycles using the structure tensor method.

3.1.3 Results

In year 1 and 2 of DISMAR, the radar signatures induced by varying bottom signatures were stored and analysed. During a period of several months an hourly acquired sequence of 256 radar images with a frame rate of 0,4 Hz were stored and analysed. Figure 3-1 shows an example of a radar image acquired on 22 March 2004 near the test site Sylt, shortly after a storm situation. Comparison of this image with an image acquired four days earlier, i.e. before the storm, using the methods outlined above and described in detail in [Z+04], yielded maps of shoal movement (distance and direction) as shown in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-1 Radar image (left) and map (right) of the Test Site Sylt. The frame in the map marks the radar survey area. The diameter length of the surveyed area is 4 km.

Figure 3-2 Maps of the distances (left) and directions (right) detected by the structure tensor. The displacements in the right map are given colour coded in [m] and directions in the left map are given in radians. The maximal displacement shown in the left map is detected over the shoal with 3 m (red). The location of the observed shoal is marked in Figure 3-1. The shoal shows a displacement of approximately 3 m (red) toward the South (yellow and green area).

During the third year of DISMAR, field tests were conducted to demonstrate the potential of a Doppler radar observing the forces gathering and transporting surface substances. For these tests the scenario of oil pollution in coastal waters was substituted by natural slicks drifting in the coastal waters. A Doppler radar was mounted onshore for the survey of a limited area within a circle of 1 nautical mile. The surveyed area was extended during the second demonstration phase (DEMO-2), a radar was mounted on board a ship to acquire Doppler scanning along the ship's track. A radar-Doppler-map was composed by single scans of an antenna, angled at 90° from the ship's heading. By the radar antenna's position and its view direction, the radar map was geo-referenced for the web-based GIS. From the Doppler scans the movements of each radial cell relative to the antenna were calculated. It could be demonstrated that the surface dynamic (in particular the forcing by wind and current), which accumulates surface substances, can be observed by this method. It allows not only finding the slick's location, but provides additionally the information to separate thick layers within a convergence from thin layers within passively drifting slicks. The measured flow speed and direction provides the base for a short time most probable drift prediction. In the case of the water surface being polluted, this information may assist in rectifying of the problem by pointing to the area of most efficient skimming. The full chain of data acquisition, processing and web presentation was tested. The near real time presentation of this actual information was demonstrated.

3.1.4 Conclusions

A Doppler radar has been used to observe and track movements of surface films, which may contain oil or oil-based material, natural film or be caused by natural phenomena like currents interaction over shallow water bottom topography. The radar has been mounted both on land and onboard a ship to test different situations. The developed algorithm is capable of finding the slick's location and can discriminate between thick and thin layers of film. In cases of pollution, the measured flow speed and direction can be used for short-term drift prediction, which can provide valuable information for planning of efficient skimming of the surface.

3.2 Ferrybox sensors

3.2.1 Introduction

A Ferrybox system with sensors for salinity, temperature, turbidity and chlorophyll-a fluorescence is operated on the ferry *Color Festival* operating from Hirtshals in Denmark to Oslo in Norway. The data are collected with software that records the sensor data and control the water sampling system. This software stores the data on log files onboard and communicates via the ship's satellite Internet connection to a data acquisition system on land, which stores them in a database. From this database the data are made available to DISPRO-2.

The Ferrybox system on the *Color Festival* has been operated by the EU-projects FerryBox and DISMAR, and has been extended with two new ferries along the Norwegian coast through national and ESA projects. In DISMAR new sensors measuring the water colour with Ramses above water radiance radiometers have been tested for future implementation on this Ferrybox system.

3.2.2 Methods

The colour of the sea, which is measured by the above water radiance radiometers, is governed by its content of dissolved and particulate material. The main optical quantities are the algal pigments (measured as Chlorophyll-a), the particulate material in general (measured as TSM) and the dissolved organic material (measured as yellow substance, CDOM). Two algorithms proposed by Marcel Wernand (at Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research), for Dutch waters, have been tested. These algorithms estimate TSM, and the algal pigment chlorophyll-a, as follows:

$$TSM (g / m^3) = 53,1 \cdot \left(\frac{Rrs(560)}{Rrs(620)} \right)^{-2,58}, \text{ Rrs}(\lambda) \text{ is reflectance measured at } \lambda \text{ nanometers}$$

$$Chl - a (mg / m^3) = 12916 \cdot \{ \text{Average} [Rrs(684) - Rrs(692)] - Rrs(672) \} + 3,5221$$

3.2.3 Results

After some initial testing on research vessels the Ramses sensor are installed and are now operational along with the *in situ* Ferrybox system on the *Color Festival* ferry in Skagerrak. Results from measurements from the ferry in July 5 and August 19 2005 has been analysed by Wernand's algorithms together with the chlorophyll-a fluorescence and turbidity respectively and are shown in Figure 3-3 and Figure 3-4. Figure 3-3 shows chlorophyll calculated from the starboard and port sensors together with chlorophyll fluorescence as well as HPLC-determined chlorophyll-a. As seen the content of chlorophyll determined from the Ramses sensors fails to give the correct value. The absolute values are a factor 3 to high in the open areas (57.5-59.0°N) and 50% too high for the Oslo Fjord area, but here the pattern to some extent are similar as obtained with the *in situ* Ferrybox sensors and the water samples. The shift in concentrations that we see in the *in situ* data are not resolved in the same way for the Ramses data and the effect of shifting from port to starboard side are a possible explanation. Around noon (58.5-59.0°N) the pattern in radiance is rather diffuse for the starboard sensor, which affects the TSM calculations even more (Figure 3-4).

TSM is calculated and plotted together with the turbidity determined by the Ferrybox-system (Figure 3-4). Typically one turbidity unit (FTU) corresponds to approximately one g/m³ TSM so the turbidity can be used as an approximation for the TSM. As seen the algorithm overestimates the TSM. Again we see that our calculated values are much higher than what the ferrybox gives, specially for the port side sensor when the ferry are in the Oslo Fjord area. It is clear that the shift in sensors as seen for the chlorophyll-a (Figure 3-3) is not fully understood and further investigation must be done.

Figure 3-5 shows MERIS-data from August 19 2005 when Ramses radiance data were compared with MERIS data from the ship transect and on 4 positions along the route. The chlorophyll calculated with Wernand's algorithms and chlorophyll products along the ships transect is shown in Figure 3-6. We first observe that the chlorophyll values from the starboard (blue) and port (green) sensors join well. Next it is clear that the Ramses-system gives much higher values than MERIS, but it must be taken into account that Wernand's algorithms are developed for other areas. New algorithms will be tuned to the Skagerrak area after some time of running and data collection. Finally, we note that in the inner

fjord (>59 degrees) (where the vicinity to land makes the satellite measurements unreliable which are flagged as “bad”) only the Ramses-system gives us data.

Figure 3-3 Content of chlorophyll-a calculated with Wernand's algorithms using the starboard (blue) and port side (green) sensors of the ship from July 5 2005, the fluorescence measured (red) by the Ferrybox-system, and determined in vitro with a HPLC method (cyan).

Figure 3-4 TSM calculated using Wernand's algorithms using the sensors on the starboard (blue) and port side (green) of Color Festival. Also the turbidity measured by the Ferrybox-system is presented (red).

Figure 3-5 RGB-image from MERIS in Skagerrak 19 August 2005. The transect of Color Festival is drawn as well as the positions for the measurements discussed in the text.

Figure 3-6 Content of chlorophyll-a determined with Ramses sensors and Wernand's algorithms (blue and green) and the MERIS chlorophyll products (red and cyan).

The reflectance spectra from Ramses and MERIS were compared on 4 positions (Figure 3-5). In the central part of Skagerrak (Figure 3-7) the footprint of the port Ramses-sensor was covered by the ship shadow. This is clearly seen in the lower reflectance and the increase towards the blue part of the spectrum.

At a new position just after the drop in calculated TSM at 58.4 (Figure 3-6) both Ramses spectra are in better agreement with the MERIS spectra (Figure 3-8) except that in the red part of the spectrum still the Ramses radiance is higher. The reason for this is that the correction for surface reflected sky radiance is too simple. For purposes where absolute values are necessary a more sophisticated reflection model must be applied; such a model will include the speed and direction of the wind in addition to the position of the sun.

The next position closer to the mouth of the outer Oslo Fjord is measured simultaneously with the MERIS pass (“match-ups”). The ship orientation relative to the sun coincidentally made both the port and starboard Ramses measurements “good” (Figure 3-9). In the violet and dark blue part (< 400 nm) of the spectrum the results from the two Ramses-sensors show some deviation, most likely due to the simple correction of surface reflected diffuse light. This deviation between the Ramses and MERIS in blue is due to a failure in the atmospheric correction for MERIS. Finally, we observe that the fluorescence peak around 685 nm, which is due to chlorophyll, is detected by both sensors.

Figure 3-7 Reflectance spectra measured in the central Skagerrak with Ramses and MERIS. Observe the difference between the starboard and port sensors, which is due to that the port footprint is covered by the ship shadow.

Figure 3-8 Reflectance spectra measured in the central Skagerrak with the two Ramses sensors and MERIS. This position is further north than in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-9 Reflectance spectra simultaneously measured (match up) in the outer Oslo Fjord with Ramses and MERIS.

Figure 3-10 Reflectance spectra in the inner part of the Oslo fjord measured with Ramses sensors and MERIS.

The spectra observed from the inner part of the Oslo fjord are presented in Figure 3-10. Here the starboard Ramses-sensors footprint is covered by shadow although this is not as clear in the spectrum as in Figure 3-7. Similarly with the outer Oslo Fjord we observe that the MERIS-spectrum is incorrect (at least for shorter wavelengths), which is due to the fact that this data is collected close to land and the MERIS satellite data are here dubious due to the well know adjacency effects.

3.2.4 Conclusions

The Ramses above water radiance sensors have been tested on research vessels and onboard the ferries. The sensor are now installed successfully and technically the sensors work properly, but new installations on ferries or other ship must test the effect from electronic noise from radars or other emitters of strong electromagnetic radiation. The radiance spectra must be carefully investigated for ship shadow and sun glint and more investigations must be performed on sky radiance corrections. The Wernand algorithms were not developed for this area, and were not expected to give correct values without training and tuning for this area, we do however see that they quite well resemble the pattern in optical signal. The comparisons with the MERIS radiance spectra showed the very well the situations where the MERIS atmospheric correction failed. The test has shown that the sensor will be an important supplement to the satellite data validation and can be used to check the marine reflectance. The fluorescence signal (FLH) from the algae was clearly seen in the spectra and could be used for detecting extreme bloom situations, but at the moment no quantitative information can be estimated from the FLH signal.

3.3 Operator controlled and automatic oil spill detection in satellite SAR data

3.3.1 Introduction

Radar sensors provide data independent of daylight and cloud conditions, making them suitable for monitoring of large ocean areas, which is difficult to monitor by other means. The SAR sensor emits a radar pulse and measures how much is scattered back from the surface (i.e. the ocean or the ground). The backscatter depends, among other things, on the surface roughness. The C-band radar backscatter (as in Radarsat and ENVISAT SARs) is caused by Bragg scattering by interaction of the incident radar waves with short gravity waves with wavelengths in the range of 5-7 cm. The capillary waves and short gravity waves are generated by winds blowing over the ocean surface. Under low wind conditions, the energy content in this part of the wave spectrum is low or almost zero, resulting in low radar backscatter and in dark patches in the SAR imagery. Surface film of high-viscosity material such as oil present on the sea surface will damp the Bragg waves, and give rise to dark signatures. Modulation of the Bragg waves by ocean current features and gravity waves can also lead to dampening giving rise to dark features. Therefore methods for both detection and discrimination of slicks are required in an operational oil spill monitoring service. The first set of methods is needed to identify potential contaminated areas, and the second to determine whether a suspicious slick is likely to contain oil or if it is more likely a result of some natural phenomena. A review of SAR backscatter from various slick types, both man-made and natural phenomena, has been given by [FHBK+05].

3.3.2 A supervised algorithm for oil spill detection

Figure 3-11 shows the main steps in a supervised algorithm for oil spill detection developed at NERSC [FHBK+05]. First, the SAR image is analysed for suspicious slicks (Step A). Secondly, after having found a slick that may contain oil, other information such as instantaneous winds and wind history are used to determine the slick type (Step B). Finally, if a slick is likely to be man-made, attempts to locate the possible emission source are made (Step C).

Step A: Does the image contain suspicious dark features?

In this step of the analysis of a new image, the operator does a visual inspection of the image to get an overview of the number of potential spills. Based on how many candidates are found, he may decide to proceed with a regular analysis of the whole image, or focus on the largest spill(s) first. This is in order to be able to keep the time schedule of one hour.

Step B: Determine slick type

When a suspicious slick has been detected, further analysis is needed to determine whether it is a man-made slick. The main steps are to determine the shape of the slick, the location relatively to surroundings and the instantaneous wind conditions. After this, additional analysis of contrast, background texture, season, geographical location, and wind history can be made. Each aspect yields a certain number of points to a candidate spill, and the total score is then translated to a "high", "medium", "low" probability label.

Step C: Determine potential source

When the analysis has established that a slick is likely to contain oil or oil-based material, it is important to try to find the emission source. Platform installations can be seen as bright spots in a SAR image, and sometimes this is also the case for ships. If the slick is connected to a bright spot in the SAR image, it is likely that it has been emitted from that location. If the analysis of the wind history supports the current shape and orientation of the slick and the wind speed has exceeded 7-8 m/s, it is even more likely that the slick contains oil, since it has survived and remained connected in such strong winds. However, ocean currents also influence the location and shape of a slick, and this must be taken into account when trying to determine a potential emission source.

Writing the oil report

It is an advantage for the users if the descriptions are using the same type of descriptions and the same approach for setting the confidence levels in the oil report. Following the algorithm in Figure 3-11 will give a basis for the report, and additional comments can be added if needed. A set of standardised messages is given in [FHBK+05].

Figure 3-11 Flow diagram for detection of slicks in SAR imagery (source: [HESS96]).

3.3.3 An example of automated slick detection

The capability of SARTool¹ to detect oil spills in ASAR-images has been tested on 11 scenes. The first 7 (from the North Sea) were selected manually because they contain highly probable oil spills. All the slicks of the subsets from the 10 images in the North Sea are detected by SARTool. Figure 3-12 shows one example of slick detection in a subset of an ASAR image. In the four images analysed for the coastal areas in the German Bight, SARTool could not identify oil slick because many structures caused by the bathymetry confused the detection algorithm.

Information about the slicks can be derived by SARTool, which marks all possible slicks with a red contour line around the slicks (Figure 3-12). The contour line turns green when the user points at the slick with the mouse. Information about the selected slick (position, size, area, perimeter etc.) can be derived. For slick detection it is possible to train a neural network to detect possible oil spills, but this requires that a collection of real oil spills are used to train the neural network before it can be used to analyse new images. An example of ASAR APP image in the German test site is shown in Figure 3-13.

The images taken in the coastal areas of the German Bight show very detailed patterns of bathymetry that makes automated detection of oil spills in SAR images impossible. The SARTool detection of potential oil spills in Figure 3-13 is not realistic and more sophisticated methods are needed which take into account bathymetry, tidal shoals and other effects in shallow waters.

¹ Analysis tool for SAR ocean analysis provided by BOOST Technologies (www.boost-technologies.com)

Figure 3-12 A subset of 2048 x 2048 pixels extracted from an ASAR scene in the North Sea on 02 Aug. 2004, where the probable slick areas have been identified by the SARTool.

Figure 3-13 ENVISAT ASAR image from 26 June 2005, acquired over the German test site where Doppler radar measurements were obtained during the field experiment performed by GKSS.

3.3.4 Conclusions

Satellite SAR sensors are capable of detecting many different ocean surface phenomena, both natural and man-made, independent of daylight and cloud conditions, and can cover large ocean areas on a regular basis. SAR data is therefore an important source of information for marine pollution monitoring. However, there is no direct relationship between the measured backscatter and the type of phenomena being imaged.

The main problem in detection of oil spills in SAR images is to discriminate between natural phenomena and slicks caused by man-made pollution, as many natural phenomena have SAR signatures similar to man-made slicks. This means that automated classification algorithms that only takes into account dark features in the images, often will identify various natural phenomena as potential oil spills. For development of more reliable information about man-made slicks, it is necessary to include ancillary data, such as meteorological data, bathymetric data, ship traffic data, position of oil rigs and location of industry along the coasts.

The operator supervised algorithm described in Section 3.3.2 is being used by the national operational oil spill monitoring service in Norway. The automated slick detection algorithm in SARTool could be used as part of this type of service to help identify dark features (slicks) that may be potential oil spills. The operator's focus could then be on investigating the spill candidates, using additional data from satellites, aircrafts, in situ instruments and numerical models, to make an improved assessment of whether an oil spill has occurred.

3.4 Automatic oil spill detection in ENVISAT ASAR imagery

3.4.1 Introduction

The availability of a huge amount of SAR images, acquired by both the European satellite ERS and the Canadian one Radarsat, has boosted the development of several oil spill detection services in different countries. Two approaches essentially have been explored, one based on the image interpretation done by experts, the second based on automatic or semi-automatic methods for identifying oil spills. The first solution can be easily adapted to several sensors and images format, but it requires trained personnel. The automatic solution, although it requires anyhow the supervision of the a human analyst, it reduces considerably the number of cases to analyse, permitting to monitor wide areas, obviously, when a different type of data is considered, it is necessary to modify the software code.

3.4.2 Methods

With the purpose of distinguishing oil spills from other similar oceanic features, in the last years we have developed a method, named 'Oil Spill Automatic Detector' (OSAD) [FGN+00], [NSG+05]. The OSAD algorithm, is able to analyse an ERS images in near real time with a computing time of about 3 minutes for a PRI image on a dual 500 MHz Pentium III PC. The system is implemented in Matera Geodesy Space Centre, where the Italian Space Agency Processing and Archiving Facility (PAF) for the European Remote Sensing (ERS) satellite sensor data and the 'Telespazio' acquisition facility are located.

A detailed description of the whole process, from satellite acquisition up to the generation of a detection report, can be found in [NSG+05].

The block diagram in Figure 3-14 shows the entire detection process.

Figure 3-14 OSAD processing chain.

3.4.3 Results

The availability of new observation capabilities, first of all ENVISAT, has encouraged us to extend the approach adopted for ERS also these data, of course it has been essential to take into account the differences among the missions. ENVISAT is particularly attractive, because it has several different acquisition modes, some of them able to cover areas up to 400 times 400 km. In this case the incidence angle ranges from 16° to 42° and the scattering mechanisms is not only the Bragg one, but also the specular one. The compensation for the incidence angle, used in the ERS case, and based on the assumption of a Bragg scattering, is not appropriate in this case. In order to estimate this compensation, a wide swath ASAR image over the ocean has been selected; the image quick look is shown in Figure 3-14. Particular attention has been paid in order to have an image with uniform intensity. The image cover a portion of Atlantic ocean near the Canary islands; the lower part (land free) has been used for the analysis. A set of one hundred range lines has been selected, averaged and the maximum value normalized to 1, as shown in Figure 3-16. A fit has been made with an exponential function. The analytical expression we have got is reported in the following.

$$F(x) = 19.4 \cdot \exp(-0.18x) + 0.06 \quad (2)$$

The other differences, like the geometric and the radiometric resolutions, have also been considered and taken into account during the image feature extraction process.

Figure 3-15 ENVISAT acquisition on Atlantic Ocean. Original data © ESA 2005.

Figure 3-16 Profile lines from ENVISAT image shown in Figure 3-15.

3.4.4 Conclusions

In order to test the modification introduced, a set of ENVISAT and ERS images, acquired on the same areas less than one hour apart, have been analysed. The differences between the homologues images are negligible and the same pattern can easily be identified. The results, produced by OSAD on ERS and ENVISAT data in high-resolution mode are practically identical, while the differences on ENVISAT wide swath mode and ERS are within 15% of the final value. The main discrepancies are found on slicks of reduced extension. This result can be explained by the fact that variance on the measurements on slick of few pixels is obviously higher, affecting negatively the classification procedure.

3.5 Automatic fusion of aircraft data for oil spill detection

3.5.1 Introduction

Marine pollution by oil spills or harmful chemicals is still one of the major environmental problems to be faced. Besides the accidental releases of pollutants the main source is assumed from the controlled release by ship traffic and oil production platforms. Since accidents or violations of regulations can never be completely excluded, precautions and instruments are needed to detect and combat maritime pollutions and a crucial element of this framework is airborne oil spill remote sensing. Like no other system, airborne pollution control is capable a) to detect possible oil spills by radar sensors, b) to verify, quantify and qualify reported pollutions by different near range sensors, c) to secure evidence against polluters and d) to coordinate clean-up operation of ships. Many nations have established such kind of airborne surveillance and also dense networks of international co-operations, since oil-spills are not restricted to national borders. One example is the Bonn agreement of 1983, establishing a trans-border observation between the North Sea adjacent states (see <http://www.bonnagreement.org/>).

3.5.2 Sensor equipment for airborne oil spill remote sensing

Since the beginning of operational aerial surveillance of marine oil pollutions in Sweden at the end of the 1970s, a defined set of remote sensors has been established as a sensor suite for airborne oil spill remote sensing. Today's sensor suites at least include a (real aperture) side-looking airborne radar (SLAR), for the far-range detection of potential marine pollution, an infrared/ultraviolet imaging system such as an IR/UV line scanner (IR/UV-LS), for the mapping of relative oil film thickness, and a camera system for visual observation. To give an example: Among the 8 contracting parties of the Bonn agreement, contributing 14 aircraft in total, all platforms are equipped with a SLAR and all but one are using IR/UV sensors (as at 2004). IR/UV devices usually operate in the thermal IR and the near UV. Furthermore, there are advanced instruments like multi-channel microwave radiometers (MWR) or laser fluorosensors (LFS) that allow measurements of oil thickness in specific thickness ranges and, with regard to laser fluorosensors, a remote classification of the spilled oil.

Figure 3-17 German maritime surveillance aircraft 57+01 (LM1) of type Do228-212 LM.

3.5.3 DISMAR & airborne oil spill remote sensing

As a contribution to the project DISMAR, five years of available data sets acquired by one of the German maritime surveillance aircraft were analysed and processed. The two German maritime surveillance aircraft, both of type Do228-212 LM (Figure 3-17), are based at the 3rd Naval Air Wing in Nordholz, Germany. Both aircraft are examples of multi-sensor platforms that carry a SLAR, an IR/UV-LS, a scanning three-channel MWR, an imaging airborne LFS (IALFS) and a forward-looking IR imaging system (FLIR). As a first step in the generation of data products from aircraft data, a sensor-specific rectification and rescaling of the remote sensing data was developed. This is necessary because aircraft attitude parameters such as roll, pitch and yaw are not accounted for by every sensor in the same way. Further processing includes the neural segmentation of ortho-rectified IR/UV oil spill images using a locally excitatory globally inhibitory oscillator network (LEGION), on the one hand, and the fusion of UV line scanner data with IALFS data on the other hand. The latter two processing steps are basic components of the Oil Spill Scene Analysis System (OSSAS) (Figure 7-1) [R05a], which allows the automated analysis and fusion of airborne remotely sensed oil spill data. Figure 3-18 shows fused NUV/IALFS images of lidar optical thickness overlaid with extracted thermal and ultraviolet features. This is the thickness map generated by OSSAS; all essential information required by the airborne sensor operator is integrated in a single map. Fused NUV/IALFS information on lidar optical thickness is included in a decision scheme for volume estimation.

Figure 3-18 Fused NUV/IALFS images of an oil plume (zoomed-out view on the left and magnified view on the right) overlaid with infrared and near ultraviolet spill contours (red and blue, respectively). The oil plume was classified by the IALFS as Diesel. Those areas with $\kappa_{o,l} > 0.2$ are marked yellow.

3.6 Comparison of satellite ocean colour data products from multiple sensors

3.6.1 Introduction

Several satellite-borne ocean colour Earth Observation (EO) sensors are presently collecting data on an operational basis. We therefore conducted a study aiming at quantifying difference in ocean colour EO sensor performances for ocean monitoring and in particular the study of algal bloom situations. The motivation for this study was to explore how data from different sensors can be utilised in one system for HAB detection and monitoring. Ocean products from the MODIS/Terra, MODIS/Aqua, MERIS, and SeaWiFS sensors have been processed and inter-compared for data acquired during the development of an early spring algal bloom in 2004 in the North Sea region. The study assesses the comparability of these OC sensors in the cases of bloom and non-bloom situations. Particular focus has been on the assessment of the quality of the MODIS/Terra data product provided by Kongsberg Spacetec AS.

3.6.2 Methods

The area covered by this study extends from 55.5°N to 60.0°N and from 4.5°E to 11.5°E, i.e. the North Sea, Skagerrak, Kattegat and the southern part of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC). Due to a complex and variable circulation pattern of the water masses in this region sub-areas with distinct optical complexity are present. Generally, the central part of the North Sea is poor on nutrients, and low density of phytoplankton is observed.

Data from the different sensors were processed by the following algorithms [Z+05]:

- MERIS – BEAM software from ESA for “algal pigment index 1” and surface reflectance products.
- MODIS/Terra – OC-3M for “Chlor a 2” products, and a semi-analytical algorithm for “Chlor a 3”.
- MODIS/Aqua – OC-3M for “Chlor a 2” products, and the standard MODIS L2 ocean product suite for normalised water-leaving radiances.
- SeaWiFS – OC4 algorithms for chlorophyll-a products.

Data from the AlgeInfo web page (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>), providing weekly updated information on the algal situation in Norwegian coastal waters, were used to assess the quality of the derived parameters from the various EO sensors. AlgeInfo gives updated information about the abundance of phytoplankton and species composition of the phytoplankton community. Most information is based on near shore data collection. The phytoplankton abundance was given as cell counts and taxonomy, as such not fulfilling the criteria for a proper validation of ocean colour EO data products. However, these data indicate the general level of phytoplankton and dominant blooming species. This information was compared with the chlorophyll a concentrations retrieved from ocean colour data.

3.6.3 Results

For comparison of data from all the four sensors, the standard chlorophyll products were presented with identical projections and visualised using the same colour scale for the chlorophyll a concentration (see Figure 3-19 for one of these dates). Visualisation of the data in such a way enabled an overview of both the general consistency between the products from the three sensors, and also the smoothness/patchiness of the retrieved parameters.

The general quality of the MODIS/Terra products was evaluated by comparison with the equivalent products from the other ocean colour sensors. Two main features were seen when performing the comparison for all dates. Firstly, the number of processed pixels in the MODIS/Terra images are for certain scenes significantly less than for the other sensors. This causes in some cases a total absence of the chlorophyll product, even for regions where the same product is properly retrieved by the other sensors. The reason for this is not clear, however the threshold for allowing data to be flagged accepted may be set too low. The quality of the raw and calibrated data should be further inspected. However, for some scenes the reason may be that the study area is very close to the outer parts of the sensor swath. The parameter settings used to run the retrieval algorithms might also be different from those used for MODIS/Aqua data, since the algorithm should be the same. Restrictions on the quality of each pixel may also apply to determine whether the pixel is processed or not. These restrictions may have been set to be too restrictive for the MODIS/Terra compared to the other sensors, causing the number of processed pixels to be significantly less for MODIS/Terra.

The other main feature observed, is that the retrieved values of chlorophyll concentrations are generally lower than for the other sensors. As this is a purely relative inter-comparison of the different sensors, we cannot say what are the true values of retrieval. However, as the MERIS, SeaWiFS and MODIS/Aqua are seen to agree very well, the low values retrieved by MODIS/Terra seems suspicious. Furthermore, some of the MODIS/Terra scenes are contaminated by stripes. The same problem is sometimes observed also for MODIS/Aqua. This phenomenon may come from the radiometric performance of the sensor and accordingly not due to the data processing.

To determine the causes for the discrepancy between results from the MODIS/Terra and the other sensors, a more detailed analysis is still required. We suggest that this analysis would include an inspection of the quality of the raw MODIS/Terra data, i.e. the radiometric performance of the sensor, and a revision of the procedures for calibration of the sensor. In the data processing chain from the raw calibrated data to the ocean products, discrepancies between sensors may occur if the atmospheric correction schemes are different. The MODIS/Aqua and MODIS/Terra data should be subject to identical algorithms for retrieval of the chlorophyll product.

Due to lack of data and the low quality of the data available from the MODIS/Terra sensor major efforts in comparison of data from the MODIS/Aqua, MERIS, and SeaWiFS sensors were undertaken. For comparison of data from these sensors, several methods of comparison have been used [Z+04]. We discuss briefly the results of intercomparison of the standard chlorophyll products here. Figure 3-20 shows the chlorophyll *a* products from these three sensors for three dates.

The selected images represent different stages of the phytoplankton bloom events that took place during this period. In the images from February 23 (Figure 3-20, row 1), the main chlorophyll distribution pattern looks similar for all sensors. The algae bloom along the Norwegian Skagerrak coast (Sørlandskysten) can be seen. High concentrations are also present in Kattegat between Denmark and Sweden. MERIS shows slightly higher concentrations along the Norwegian coast than the two other sensors. Also, the chlorophyll *a* concentrations retrieved by MERIS in central Skagerrak is around 2mgm^{-3} which is twice as high as values retrieved by MODIS/Aqua and SeaWiFS.

For March 9, the agreement between MODIS/Aqua and SeaWiFS are still very good, while MERIS shows generally lower values along the Norwegian Skagerrak coast (Figure 3-20, row 2). Both MODIS/Aqua and SeaWiFS retrieve high pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak. Whether these observations are consistent with the *in situ* observed blooms of *Chattonella* for the same time period is uncertain, due to the lack of offshore field observations. For this date the MERIS Case 2 water flags indicated the presence of Case 2 waters in large parts of the area. Using the MERIS Algal 2 product, which should be more adequate for this type of water, improved the agreement between MERIS and the other sensors for some areas. Images from April 1 (Figure 3-20, row 3) show generally good agreement between all three sensors. However, due to atmospheric correction contamination around the southern part of Norway, the number of unprocessed pixels for MERIS and SeaWiFS are rather high. Increased levels of chlorophyll *a* are again observed along the Norwegian coast east of Lindesnes (Skagerrak Coast).

3.6.4 Conclusions

The conclusion of the study is that the MODIS/Terra products were inconsistent with equivalent products derived from the other EO ocean colour sensors, and with the current processing these products are not satisfactory for use of the data in an operational system for algae bloom monitoring in Norwegian coastal waters. We suspect the discrepancies to be mostly caused by the radiometric performance and the calibration procedure used for the MODIS/Terra sensor. A further harmonisation with the processing tools and algorithms used should be done using similar tools being developed and validated by NASA. To validate the products with the new processing scheme, parallel processing of MODIS/Terra and –Aqua data as well as SeaWiFS data should be undertaken. It should also be considered to use the NASA SeaDAS OC4 software or other operational software implemented and tested by NASA.

Figure 3-19 Distribution of chlorophyll in the North Sea/ Skagerrak region on April 1, 2004 as retrieved by the MERIS, MODIS/Terra, MODIS/Aqua, and SeaWiFS sensors. The satellite overpass time is indicated (UTC time). The name of the products and/or the name of the algorithms are given. For MODIS/Terra products resulting from two different retrieval algorithms are shown.

Regardless of the poor quality of the MODIS/Terra data, the presented results have shown a generally good consistency between the products from the MERIS, MODIS/Aqua and SeaWiFS sensors. The atmospheric correction scheme has shown to be more robust for MERIS than for the other two sensors, avoiding negative (non physical) values in the blue part of the spectrum. Agreement between the major patterns of chlorophyll distribution as retrieved by the different sensors has been shown. However, some discrepancies between retrieved chlorophyll *a* concentrations have been observed. The discrepancies have been most obvious when comparing values averaged over small areas and become less pronounced when averaging over larger areas. The study shows better agreement between MODIS/Aqua and SeaWiFS, than between MERIS and any of the other two sensors. This is most likely due to the similarity in atmospheric correction scheme and chlorophyll retrieval algorithms that are used for these two sensors, as well as a minimum difference in the overpass time between the two sensors.

The overall conclusion of this study is that all sensors evaluated, with the exception of MODIS/Terra, provide the information required for a system for detection and monitoring of harmful algal blooms (HABs).

Figure 3-20 Chlorophyll distribution in North Sea and Skagerrak region as retrieved by the MERIS, MODIS/Aqua, and SeaWiFS (from left to right) for February 23, March 9 and April 1, 2004 (from top to bottom). Black areas indicate unprocessed pixels (clouds, corrupt atmospheric correction, or out of swath areas). Data are plotted with the same logarithmic colour scale, as indicated by the colour bar. The unit is mgm^{-3} . Copyright: ESA/NASA/Orbimage.

3.7 NRT processing of ocean colour and surface temperature data

3.7.1 Introduction

In DISMAR, PML undertook near-real time operational processing of existing satellite EO data and developed new capabilities based on new sensors in support of algal bloom monitoring. Ocean colour (OC) data were of prime interest providing surface spatio-temporal variability in chlorophyll (as a measure of phytoplankton abundance) with sea-surface temperature (SST) showing surface structure related to the underlying physical processes that frequently govern the biological variability. These data were then made available in near-real time and in various temporal composite forms to the DISPRO demonstrator. Finally, techniques were investigated to discriminate harmful from non-harmful species using MERIS data

3.7.2 Methods

The operational production of SST used the two NOAA AVHRR instruments (following [MGM+97]). The OC data were initially produced from the SeaWiFS sensor following the methods of [LG99]; however, with the non-renewal by NASA of the data access agreement with Orbimage (the company that owns SeaWiFS) OC data were produced operationally from the two NASA-MODIS sensors [S+05a] and MERIS [S+05c]. Briefly, MODIS data were obtained from either the UK receiving station at Dundee or NASA and automatically processed from level 1 where necessary to produce georeferenced chlorophyll and radiance maps on the same projection as the SST and SeaWiFS data. MERIS data were obtained in level 2 format from the ESA 7-day rolling archive and processed in a similar manner to MODIS. The metadata associated with each pass were stored in an SQL database linked to the demonstrator.

3.7.3 Results

SST data were processed continually throughout the project covering the English Channel and the Norwegian HAB demonstration area. Considering both areas there were approximately 10,000 scenes processed in total providing daily coverage less cloud masking; to compensate for cloud, weekly composites were also produced for the time series. OC data were produced from SeaWiFS up to December 2004 comprising ~1800 scenes including the 2003 and 2004 summer bloom periods of the target HAB species *Karenia mikimotoi*. Operational processing of MODIS started in 2004 and of MERIS early 2005 providing a continuation of the OC service for the final year of the project and covering the 2005 bloom. The algorithms developments enabled OC data to be available from three sensors instead of just SeaWiFS, though as noted in [Z+05] MODIS-Terra data had calibration problems that made the products in many cases unusable. Chlorophyll weekly composites were also produced for the sensors improving the spatial coverage.

Some example MERIS data for 2 August 2005 are shown in Figure 3-21, together with MODIS Aqua and MODIS Terra ocean colour data for the same day and an AVHRR sea-surface temperature for the previous evening (1 August). The images were taken during the summer blooming "period" of *Karenia mikimotoi*, but the most notable feature is the relatively low chlorophyll concentrations in the central western English Channel. The low Chla on this and subsequent images is believed to be caused by unseasonably high winds at the end of July that disrupted the water vertical structure possibly preventing formation of the "usual" bloom. The ocean colour images in Figure 3-21a-c are a best case scenario since all three satellites show the western English Channel (WEC) towards the centre of each swath. Over these latitudes, the viewing geometry and narrow swath of MERIS mean that the WEC is not viewed every ~3 days. With MODIS-Aqua or MODIS-Terra the WEC is usually imaged but every ~3 days is located at the edge of the swath with concomitant poor chlorophyll retrievals.

The combined SeaWiFS/MERIS & MODIS data sets provided continuous near-real time OC coverage as would be required for an operational algal bloom monitoring service. It also enabled evaluation of the interannual variability of algal blooms including *K. mikimotoi*. In 2003 the bloom was particularly intense and appeared ~1 month earlier (June of July) and extended further east than usual. This was possibly a result of the hot weather during Summer 2003 (see [Z+04]). By contrast in 2005 there were no significant blooms with only small patches present by early August: as noted above this was probably due to poor weather at the end of July mixing the water column. In 2004 the bloom was visible in July with lower concentrations than in 2003. It is planned to use these results, together with the algal bloom model (see section 3.11), in a publication on the interannual variations of this harmful species.

Figure 3-21 Chlorophyll-*a* images from a) MERIS (10:51UT), b) MODIS Terra (11:24) and c) MODIS-Aqua (13:00) for 2 August 2005; d) SST image from AVHRR for 1 August 2005 (21:53UT).

The multivariate HAB classifier was applied to MERIS data from 2003 over a known bloom of *K. mikimotoi*. Results were similar to SeaWiFS data (see [Z+05]) and were presented at the ENVISAT MERIS/AATSR workshop [S+05c]. There was clear discrimination of the HAB regions but the classifier also marked the high reflectance coccolithophore blooms off Brittany (France), which may be false alarms or alternatively may be due to a mixed population of coccolithophores and *K. mikimotoi*. A new spatial anomaly detection technique was also developed to attempt to remove false positives: and results were presented at a SPIE annual European Symposium, Sept. 2005 in Belgium [S+05b]. Good automatic detection of the coccolithophore bloom has been achieved and the performance analysis of this approach is ongoing.

3.7.4 Conclusions

All the planned objectives were achieved: a continuous near-real time data stream for SST and OC was maintained throughout DISMAR through use of existing and new processing methods developed in the project. Additional products such as temporal composites and a HAB classifier for MERIS were produced in response to user feedback. Finally, a number of presentations and papers have been given or are in preparation based on this work (see e.g. [S+05a] and [S+05c]).

3.8 Combination of MERIS-Landsat for Mucilage detection

Mucilage is a foamy aggregate of organic matter, present on the surface and/or the water column. The phenomenon is peculiar to Italian seas, especially the North Adriatic: the significant part of the organic matter is present in sea waters in a dissolved or colloidal state (95%), produced by bacteria and microalgae exudation, essentially as sugar. Several factors (physical and climatic) may act in order to facilitate aggregation of this matter.

Gel aggregates ranging from 0.5 mm to some tenths of centimetres are common both in open oceanic sea and in coastal waters, e.g. in river mouths, bays or lagoons ("planktonic snow") while in the Adriatic Sea mucilage are made up by a complex gathering of amorphous organic and inorganic matter, absorbing phytoplankton cells, bacteria and faecal matter. Due to the peculiar physiography of the North Adriatic Sea (shallow waters, gulf shaped sea), wide aggregates are often reported in the water column.

In the framework of the successful ESA CAT 1 proposal prepared by the DISMAR Project, MERIS (see Figure 3-22) data were selected, ordered and acquired. Considering the low spatial resolution of the MERIS satellite products, also Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 data have been exploited (see Figure 3-23).

Figure 3-22 MERIS image (11 June 2003), RGB elaboration.

Table 3-1 lists the MERIS images that have been ingested into the repository of the Italian node of the DISPRO System.

Table 3-1 MERIS images used in the study of Mucilage.

Product number	Product Name	Product Acronym	Size	Acquisition Date
1	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	24 June 2004
2	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	19 July 2003
3	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	30 June 2004
4	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	03 July 2004
5	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	19 August 2002
6	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	11 June 2003
7	MERIS Full Resolution Level 1b	MER_FR_1P	650 km length	27 June 2004

Figure 3-23 Landsat image of 02 July 2004 with administrative boundaries.

The presence of mucilage has been detected through analysis of the available satellite images, exploiting the available E-Cognition SW package. The main output are represented as shapefiles showing objects classified as mucilage (see Figure 3-24).

The E-Cognition SW is a package that allows to perform advanced analysis on images, based on an object oriented approach: attribution criteria for the different classes are not applied to the pixels, but to the basic components of images, called "objects".

The preliminary elaboration is then a segmentation, following that the objects to be classified are extracted, based on different radiometric and shape parameters that can be selected and modified by the operator. Segmentation can be performed in order to take into account the geometrical scale peculiar of the phenomenon to be highlighted, then information derived from segmentations performed at different levels can be combined in order to obtain more precise classifications.

Figure 3-24 Example of mucilage detected on a Landsat image.

3.9 The met.no oil spill fate forecast system

Met.no's oil spill fate forecasting system has served Norwegian authorities for more than 15 years. At the start of DISMAR, it was a single legacy code using proprietary file formats and manual execution by a duty meteorologist. In order to meet the requirements of DISPRO, the system has been partly recoded with the aim of separating the operations into three modules: (1) an input module that acquires simulation parameters from the user and accesses the relevant operational forcing data streams; (2) the oil fate model that calculates the motion and evolution of the oil; and (3) an output module that formats the simulation results for delivery to a range of users.

Input module: The accessing of forcing data has not been developed to any advanced level in DISMAR, since the project aim is to demonstrate a service for Norwegian national waters. This is the default for the new input module and is adapted directly from the original system. It accesses the default set of forcing data, which is obtained from met.no's operational models for northern Europe: (a) wind and air temperature from the weather forecasting model HIRLAM, (b) wave height and Stokes drift from the wave forecast model WAM; (c) 3D currents, temperature and salinity from the ocean forecast model MIPOM. For obtaining the simulation parameters from the user, a web-based order form (Figure 3-25) has been developed and implemented. Submission of a valid order form automatically starts an oil spill model simulation that typically completes within a few minutes.

Oil spill fate model: OD3D calculates the drift and chemical evolution of a marine oil spill in the guise of a number of "superparticles," each of which represents a certain amount of oil or its by-products. The user may choose from a range of oil types for the spilled oil. The oil slick is modified by advection due to currents and by weathering (evaporation, dispersion, emulsification) due to exposure to air, water and waves over time. In addition, the model includes a novel deep blowout sub-model for oil sources below the surface. The core of OD3D has been developed in cooperation with SINTEF (Trondheim, Norway) and has not been modified in DISMAR.

Output module: This has been the main effort in DISMAR. Output from OD3D is a binary file containing a full description of each superparticle at each time step of the simulation, as well as all user-supplied information describing the spill. A set of filters has been written to format the results for a number of users, including: (1) a specified format for the Norwegian Coastal Authority for direct ingestion in their proprietary crisis response tool, (2) a special format for visualization using met.no's digital analysis tool, and (3) an ASCII format for ingestion in the met.no DISPRO node (metoc.met.no).

The revised system has been used to emulate a forecast service for oil spill incidents. The user requests a simulation by accessing the order form on met.no's password-protected web portal for registered users. Within minutes, results are sent directly to the met.no DISPRO node where they are rendered for display in DISPRO-2 (see Figure 3-26).

Data from met.no's operational weather, wave and ocean-ecosystem forecasting models are also made available on the DISPRO node as ancillary information for decision-making, both for oil spill and HAB crisis situations.

Figure 3-25 Screen shot of the met.no oil spill simulation order form. It is accessed through the password-protected portal kilden.met.no. The user fills in the details of the oil spill and desired output form for the results. For DISMAR, the results are sent to <http://metoc.met.no>, which is the met.no DISPRO node. A simulation using OD3D typically takes 5-10 minutes from submission until the results are viewable in DISPRO (Figure 3-26).

Figure 3-26 Screen shot of DISPRO-2 showing real-time simulation data from met.no's operational oil spill model in the Skagerrak. Shown is surface oil concentration (grey shading), along with significant wave height (contours) and mean direction (arrows) from the wave forecast model, and overlaid coastline and political boundary base layers.

3.10 Oil drift model for the Adriatic Sea

3.10.1 Introduction

A simple drift model has been used to monitor and forecast the position of the oil spill; the algorithm is driven by archived data: wind on sea surface, surface currents from sea models, meteorological data. The model is based on the following assumption: Oil drift is mainly driven by wind induced surface currents.

This approach is intended as a very fast response to emergencies, in order to roughly estimate slick behaviour while waiting results from more sophisticated drift models. It is suitable to be integrated in an oil spill automatic detector, in order to let users simultaneously know not only slick position but also its dynamics.

3.10.2 Methods

The oil spill is identified by its centre of mass (read on oil spill detector output) and described by means of its contour, produced as a text file by the detection algorithm itself; starting from a known position, detected by SAR or by direct observation, a time series of position data is generated for the following 24 hours.

Drift is modelled as composed of 3 different contributions:

- Wind induced drift: Slick contour points move with a speed evaluated as a percentage of wind speed (in our area 3,3%)
- Slick spread: Contour points move away from slick barycentre; spread velocity is given by a constant term plus an additional term along wind direction
- Random contour evolution: A random term is added, proportional to absolute wind magnitude, in order to describe slick contour fragmentation.

The model coefficients have been computed on a dataset of oil spill "double detections": starting from a list of verified oil spills (detected by direct observation) we have found for almost all cases SAR images acquired up to 2 days before or after, in which the same slicks were visible, letting us evaluate mean displacement at given marine conditions. Moreover, if during the operational use of the model a new oil spill "double detection" becomes available, the model can self-tune according to the observed shift. However, this kind of approach is intended to be used in a limited area with well defined characteristics.

As input data, the model exploits: (1) the Oil spill detector (OSAD) output; and (2) all available ancillary data (wind, currents...). In our demonstration we have used data freely available on the net, such as wind fields from NASA's QuickScat satellite.

As output data, the model produces: (1) position and shape of the oil spill, at fixed times (in DISMAR we have selected 6, 12, 18 and 24 hours after detection), and (2) surface currents and all data derived from ancillary data.

The main model output is the position and shape of the oil slick(s), delivered as a time series of text files, each one containing the slick contour at a fixed time after acquisition; contour files are also converted to shapefiles in order to be used by the Italian MapServer (every shapefile contains all slicks in a same SAR image). Surface currents and all data derived from ancillary data can also be delivered to users.

3.10.3 Results

Figure 3-27(a) shows the predicted drift for six oil spills identified in an ERS-1 SAR image over the Adriatic Sea on February 8, 2000. The main model output is the position and shape of the oil spill(s), delivered as a time series of contour lines at a fixed time after the initial observation. Available wind information was used as input to the model, together with the initial position of the spills identified by the OSAD system (Figure 3-27(b)).

Figure 3-27 Predicted oil drift overlaid on an ERS-1 SAR image. Original SAR data © ESA 2000.

3.10.4 Conclusions

In DISMAR the oil drift model for the Adriatic Sea has been refined and optimised. During the two demonstration phases, it has been applied to oil spills detected by the OSAD system, and presented to end-users via the Italian DISPRO node. The model provides a rapid estimate of oil spill drift, and as such is well suited for inclusion in an operational systems, allowing the operator to investigate the dynamics of an oil spill.

3.11 Ecological model

3.11.1 Introduction

A coupled hydrodynamic-ecosystem model was developed for the western English Channel (WEC) in order to simulate blooms of the harmful dinoflagellate *Karenia mikimotoi*. The model was developed in hindcast mode and thoroughly tested to ensure confidence in the model ability to reproduce the observed physical and biological structure.

3.11.2 Method

The DISMAR model was based on the POLCOMS-ERSEM 3D model that outputs 51 pelagic variables. Phytoplankton is split into four functional sub-groups: diatoms, flagellates, picophytoplankton and dinoflagellates and *Karenia mikimotoi* was introduced as a separate, motile dinoflagellate HAB species. The model was comprehensively validated with remotely sensed data and various observational data collected in situ at sampling stations within the model domain. Cost functions were used to quantitatively evaluate the model performance and highlight areas that needed to be improved; mean X values less than 1.0 indicate that the differences between the model and observational data are less than the variability of the data and the model has some level of predictive skill.

3.11.3 Results

Model fields were produced in hindcast mode throughout the DISPRO-2 demonstration. As an example, Figure 3-28(a) shows surface total chl_a for 30 July 2005. This compared well to remotely sensed chl_a for 2 August (Figure 3-28(b)) with the model capturing the higher concentrations along the tidal front in the WEC (Western English Channel).

Figure 3-28 Total model surface chlorophyll 30 July 2005; b MODIS-Aqua chl-a for 2 August (units for both m^{-3}).

Comparison of the model with *in situ* data collected at station L4 (50°15'N, 04°13'W, water depth ~55m) indicated confidence in the ability to simulate temperature (Figure 3-29, $X=0.2735$, $r^2=0.9289$), nitrate (figure 3-30, $X=0.6640$, $r^2=0.6784$) and silicate (Figure 3-30, $X=0.9867$, $r^2=0.3521$) but less confidence in modelling observed phosphate (Figure 3-30, $X=1.1850$, $r^2=0.4564$). Results are less impressive for phytoplankton. Extensive model validation highlighted systematic errors in the model with regards to the timing of the phytoplankton blooms. For example, a reduction in the diatom basal respiration term was shown to delay the diatom bloom in the model by approximately 30 days at L4, which is more realistic when compared to observations: Figure 3-31 shows the diatom carbon biomass at L4 in the model for a simulation of 2003. 'Model old' indicates the model results with the original basal respiration parameterisation and 'model new' indicates the results after this value has been increased.

Figure 3-29 Depth-mean temperature at station L4: model against *in-situ* observations.

Figure 3-30 Model nutrients against in-situ nutrients observed at station L4.

Figure 3-31 Modelled diatoms with changed basal respiration term $srsP1x$ (model old: 0.15, model new: 0.05). X-axis is Julian Day in 2003.

3.11.4 Conclusions

The DISMAR model has produced promising results that were used operationally in hindcast mode in DISPRO-2. The predicative capability varied between different output variables and there is further scope for improvement.

4 Metadata and data harmonisation

4.1 Review of standards for geographic metadata and data

Developing a web-based GIS with multiple data providers required harmonisation of data and metadata to facilitate access to distributed and heterogeneous repositories. Data harmonisation, i.e. the process of making multi-source data and product repositories interoperable, was thus closely linked to the DISPRO development. Harmonisation also involves making metadata interoperable, both *discovery metadata* (i.e. metadata used by DISPRO to locate and download products) and *technical metadata* (i.e. metadata needed by the prototype to be able to manipulate a product, e.g. overlay it correctly on a map or another product). Discovery metadata must include spatial and temporal coverage of the product, and possibly other metadata elements that will help the user make meaningful searches for products, for instance, what parameters they contain. Technical metadata must include all necessary information required by DISPRO to enable proper manipulation and display of the product.

Existing standards for geographic metadata and data were reviewed and evaluated (Table 4-1), to find a flexible and extensible solution to the interoperability problem. This work led to an initial recommendation to implement a metadata structure compliant with the Core Metadata element set of ISO 19115, and to encode it in XML. As no standard XML encoding was available during the project, the partners developed a schema using W3C XML Schema, the DISPRO metadata schema, to represent the chosen ISO 19115 profile. [HOTu05] describes this metadata specification in detail.

The majority of data in DISMAR were raster or other gridded data. Thus, the OGC WMS (Web Map Service) specification was found to be best suited for data handling and display. A mature WMS server and client tool, the UMN (University of Minnesota) MapServer, was subsequently selected for implementing the DISPRO system. MapServer is also capable of handling vector data, enabling both raster and vector data to be displayed on the same map, in a projection selected by the user. MapServer handles a series of formats for raster and vector data, as well as spatially enabled databases. The partners were thus free to provide their products in many different formats, among others, TIFF, GeoTIFF and JPEG, for raster data, and Shapefiles for vector data. Two partners also stored their data in a database, generating metadata and data files requested by the MapServer on the fly. The database systems used, were PostgreSQL and ArcIMS.

Table 4-1 Selected standards for geographic data and metadata.

Standard / Reference	Description
GML (Geography Markup Language) [OGC04c]	An XML encoding for storage and exchange of geographic information, incorporating both spatial and non-spatial properties. Conforms with several of OGC's Abstract Specifications [OGC03a] and ISO standards for geographic information, among others, ISO 19115.
ISO 19115 (Geographic Information – Metadata) [ISO03b]	Metadata standard for geographic data developed by ISO/TC 211, defined as an UML model. ISO 19139 will provide an XML encoding of ISO 19115.
CSML (Climate Science Mark-Up Language) [W+04]	A GML application schema, developed by the NERC Data Grid project (UK), for storage and exchange of climate related data and metadata.
DC (Dublin Core) [DC03a]	A general standard for describing online resources, but also includes elements for describing location and time of geographic data sets.
TIFF (Tagged Image File Format) [Rit97]	A general-purpose raster format that handles black & white, greyscale and colour images. Widely used in image processing, publishing, etc.
GeoTIFF [Geo03]	Extension of TIFF format, with headers for geographic metadata, such as position (tie point), map projection, datum, etc.
NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) [Uni03]	Binary format for storage of array-oriented data in a platform independent manner. Widely used in e.g. the numerical modelling community.
HDF (Hierarchical Data Format) [NCSA03]	Binary format for storage of multi-dimensional arrays of data, including point series, images and gridded data. Often used for satellite images.
GRID (Gridded Binary) [WMO92]	WMO standard for storage and exchange of gridded meteorological data.
BUFR (Binary Universal Form for the Representation of Meteorological Data) [WMO95]	WMO standard for storage and exchange of point meteorological data.
Shapefiles [ESRI98]	A general-purpose vector data format developed by ESRI. Industry standard in the GIS community.

4.2 Development of harmonised products for demonstration in DISPRO

Figure 4-1 illustrates the main steps and subsystems in the production of products for distribution to users via the DISMAR prototype. Initial data acquisition from remote or in situ sensors, as well as model forecasts of future met-ocean or pollution situations, are done by dedicated systems, often operated by external actors. These systems place their data in repositories accessible to one or more partners. Products are then generated with partners' in-house systems, termed Product Generators, and stored in legacy system formats, which may be an internal format or a standard format, and which may include a variable amount of metadata. All software and formats used up to and including the Product Generators need not change as they are not affected by the DISPRO tools and standards.

In order to make the products interoperable each data provider implemented an OGC WMS interface to their data repository, converting legacy formats, as required, to the data formats supported by their WMS implementation. Each WMS server instance, called a DISPRO Node, runs on a standard HTTP server. Two major DISPRO subsystems, the DISPRO Portal and the DISPRO Client, were also based on Open GIS compliant software, including the UMN MapServer, various XML processing tools and an native XML database (eXist). The DISPRO portal and WMS client also run on a standard HTTP server, while each end-user accesses the services through a standard web browser on his local computer.

Figure 4-1 Schematic view of producers' processing chains for DISMAR demonstrations.

The processing chain illustrated in Figure 4-1 provides a high degree of flexibility for the producers, as they need not alter any of their internal systems, but just add on conversion tools to make products interoperable with the DISMAR prototype. In addition, a WMS server needs to be installed to set up a DISPRO node.

4.3 Metadata and data formats in DISPRO

Metadata are used by DISPRO to describe the DISPRO Nodes and the individual layers. These metadata (also known as service metadata) are stored in the WMS server's mapfile [McK05]. The description of a DISPRO Node is done as shown in Figure 4-2, exemplified for the CMRC DISPRO Node. The `NAME` attribute uniquely identifies the DISPRO Node, while the attributes in the `WEB/METADATA` element give further information about the node. For DISPRO, the most important attribute is `wms_onlineresource`, with the URL to the mapfile that contains the layers offered by the node.

```

MAP
  NAME "CMRC_DISPRO-2"
  ...
  WEB
    METADATA
      "wms_title" "The OGC WMS from CMRC for Dispro"
      "wms_onlineresource" "http://143.239.249.67/cgi-bin/mapserv?
        map=/home/dismar/dispro-wms-groups.map&"
      "wms_contactperson" "Eamonn O Tuama"
      "wms_contactorganization" "CMRC"
    END
  END
  ...
END

```

Figure 4-2 Metadata for a DISPRO Node.

Each layer also has to be described in the mapfile. This is done by a set of metadata elements inside each layer description, as illustrated in Figure 4-3, which are used for a vector layer. DISPRO uses the various parts of the metadata to: (1) position the data correctly on a map when displayed, (2) controlling how the layer is displayed, (3) providing ancillary information supporting interpretation of the displayed data, (4) facilitate searching for data or finding recently added data, and (5) references to data and metadata files used by DISPRO. [HOTu05] gives a full description of the layer description in DISPRO.

```

MAP
  ...
  LAYER
    METADATA
      "wms_srs" "EPSG:29900 EPSG:4326"
      "wms_title" "Coastline"
      "wms_layer_group" "/vector/base"
      "wms_keywordlist" "datestamp:2005-05-24, coast,
        coastline, high water mark"
      "wms_abstract" "1:10,000 coastline polygon of
        Ireland, based on the High Water
        Mark line in the OSI High Water Mark
        / Low Water Mark dataset."
      "wms_metadataurl_href" "[base-url]/dismar/metadata"
      "wms_metadataurl_format" "text/xml"
      "wms_metadataurl_type" "TC211"
      "wms_style" "dispro"
      "wms_style_dispro_legendurl_href" "[base-url]/dismar/legends/
        legend-coastline.png"
      "wms_style_dispro_legendurl_width" "125"
      "wms_style_dispro_legendurl_height" "100"
      "wms_style_dispro_legendurl_format" "image/png"
    END
    NAME "coast_pl"
    DATA coastline/coast_pl
    STATUS ON
    TYPE polygon
    CLASS
      NAME "coastline"
      COLOR 255 248 220
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
    PROJECTION
      "init=epsg:29900" # Irish National Grid
    END
  END # end of layer object
  ...
END

```

Figure 4-3 Metadata for a vector layer.

4.4 The DISPRO metadata schema

Metadata in DISPRO have been harmonised through the definition of an ISO 19115 profile including the Core Metadata element set, and has been defined in an XML schema [HOTu05].

Figure 4-4 shows the top-level elements of the DISPRO metadata schema. First, there are six elements used to identify and characterise the metadata file itself. The `MetadataStandardName` and `MetadataStandardVersion` identify the file as a DISPRO metadata file, and documents which version of the schema is used. Two different versions were used in the project, one for DISPRO-1 and one for DISPRO-2. The two versions are nearly identical; the second extends the first with a few new elements, and is the one shown in this report. The third element, `FileIdentifier`, provides a unique reference to the metadata file, typically in the form of an URL. Then, the `Language` and `CharacterSet` elements specify what language the metadata are encoded in, e.g. "en" for English, and which character set the file is stored in, e.g. "utf8". The language codes are defined according to ISO 639-2 [LOC05]. The sixth element, `DateStamp`, provides the date the metadata file was generated, formatted as CCYY-MM-DD, e.g. 2005-08-12 for 12 August 2005.

The next element, `DataSetURI`, describes in free text format, the Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) of the dataset to which the metadata instance applies.

The `MetadataContact` element provides contact information for the person or organisation responsible for generating and maintaining the metadata, including a reference to online information that can be used to contact the responsible person or organisation. The `DataIdentification` element provides similar contact information for the person or organisation that is responsible for the dataset on which the layer is based. One or more keywords can be associated with a dataset. The keywords can be taken from a globally established thesaurus, e.g. GCMD [NASA05], or from a thesaurus defined by a smaller user community. Other information about a dataset includes, among others, the (file) format, language and character set used in the dataset, as well as a description of its spatial resolution geo-spatial extent.

In addition to the above metadata elements, the DISPRO metadata schema contains elements for describing geo-referencing of the dataset (elements `ReferenceSystem` and `MapProjection`), the data source (`DataGenerator`) and parameters contained (`ParameterDescription`), information about distribution of the (full) dataset, e.g. in its original format and resolution (`DataDistribution`), and a quality measures for the dataset (`DataQuality`).

Finally, there are two elements specifically included for the DISPRO application, `DataGroup` and `OGC_WMS`. The first provides a grouping mechanism for data, enabling searching for data related to specific events, e.g., the Prestige accident. The second element, `OGC_WMS`, provides attributes (`wms_name`, `service`) used specifically by DISPRO to allow the metadata instance to provide a GetMap link to the data described. This element is used in conjunction with the information in an "wms_services.xml" (stores on each node) file to generate the OGC GetMap request (see [OTu05]).

4.5 Experiences and recommendations from the harmonisation process

During the course of the project, partners have built competence and capacity in a broad range of web and GIS related standards, technologies and tools. The complexity and rapid changes within these fields made the integration of different technologies and tools in DISPRO a challenging task. On the providers' side, DISPRO nodes (WMS servers) had to be set up and maintained as specifications and implementations evolved. On the DISMAR service side, the DISPRO portal and DISPRO client had to be revised and extended to meet both advances in specifications and implementations, while taking on board new user requirements. As the system evolved, the products, including metadata, had to be revised to comply with the latest specifications, and wherever feasible, the process chain generating the WMS compatible data and metadata automated. Through the DISPRO development and demonstrations, a number of practical aspects of establishing and maintaining a distributed web-based GIS system yielded valuable insight in the infrastructure needed for providing GMES services in an operational context.

On the whole, both providers and end-users have overall positive experiences with the development and validation of DISPRO. The major benefit for providers is that they can retain their processing

chain, including any legacy systems, up to the point of data/metadata delivery, and need only develop format transformation routines if their original formats are different from the formats supported by their OGC WMS server of choice. Public domain software is available for setting up a DISPRO node, i.e., a WMS server. Several web-based commercial GIS also supports the WMS specification, so providers that have purchased a COTS GIS can also use this to make their products available through the DISPRO system. The major benefit for the users is that they need no special software to access the system; a common web browser will do. Another benefit is that DISPRO also offers the opportunity of downloading data sets, through a web-based link in the metadata specification.

Further development of DISPRO into a (pre-)operational GMES service, must build on the standards employed in the project, and support for features and coverages should be added by incorporation of WFS [OGC02c] and WCS [OGC03d] servers.

Figure 4-4 Top-level elements of the DISPRO metadata schema.

5 DISPRO prototype development

The DISPRO prototype implements an OGC Web Map Service (WMS) system [OGC04] and is accessible through the portal at <http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dismar/index.xml>. It consists of a set of distributed data nodes, each providing an OGC WMS interface, and a portal that communicates with the nodes and provides various client applications such as a map viewer, profiler, and metadata catalogue. The implementation of the system relies heavily on Java and XML technologies, with the Open Source University of Minnesota (UMN) MapServer [UMN05], running as a CGI application under the Apache [ASF05] web server providing the core web GIS client and OGC WMS (both client and server) functionality.

The main components of DISPRO are the catalogue, the profiler, and the web GIS. These components are described below. A full description of the architecture and implementation of the DISPRO prototype is given in [OTu03] and [OTu05].

5.1 The Catalogue

The catalogue forms the core of the DISPRO system. It stores data derived from the capabilities files returned by each participating node in response to a GetCapabilities request issued by the portal aggregator. A capabilities file consists of information about the WMS node itself and about each map layer that it can serve. It is this aggregated dataset that underpins DISPRO, and it is updated continually every 15 minutes. The update frequency of the polling daemon can be changed as needed.

The catalogue system (Figure 5-1) incorporates a number of sub components - aggregator, database, web client interface. These are described in turn.

Figure 5-1 The DISPRO catalogue system.

The aggregator is implemented as a simple Python script that is scheduled by the server to run at regular intervals. It contains directives to call each node in turn for its capabilities file, apply an XSLT stylesheet to the returned capabilities files to extract the layer data, and upload the resulting XML files to the DISPRO database. The system can be easily extended to include new nodes by adding their capabilities URL to the Python script.

The database is implemented using the Open Source native XML database eXist [EDO05]. This integrates particularly well with web service type applications: it provides an efficient way of storing and querying XML documents without the overhead of converting the XML to relational tables, storing and querying a relational database, and converting the result set tables back to XML/HTML for display. The eXist database relies on the Apache Cocoon [APC05] XML publishing framework for processing XML files and communicating with the data store and web client.

The web clients interfacing to the database are of the thin client type (i.e. based on standard HTML and JavaScript). There are two main interfaces, one providing a form for querying the catalogue and displaying metadata abstracts and full discovery metadata, the other, a standard part of eXist, allowing a user with administrative privileges to manage the database (update, delete, set users, etc.).

5.2 The Profiler

The profiler interface is a web form that allows the user to set and store their preferences for several key variables in DISPRO, i.e. map projection, geographic bounding box, and layer groups (e.g. oil, algae, emergency, etc.). Each time the profile web page (http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dispro/bbox-and-layers_query.xml) is opened, a query is triggered to the catalogue regarding the available map projections and layer groups available. The results are presented to the user who can then enter the bounding box coordinates, and select the projection and layer groups from amongst those displayed. When the completed form is then submitted, only those map layers matching the preferences are returned from the catalogue and used to populate the GIS client.

5.3 The Web GIS

The web GIS interface allows a user to view the map layers in the particular geographic bounding box and map projection previously selected using the profile form. Standard functions such as select/deselect layer, and pan, zoom and centre are provided, all relying on basic web browser capabilities (no plug-ins required). At the middleware level, the GIS is implemented using UMN MapServer [UMN05] which acts as both web GIS client and OGC WMS client. UMN MapServer runs as a CGI application of the Apache HTTP web server. The OGC WMS Client extends the functionality of a standalone web map serving application to allow it to retrieve maps using the OGC GetMap request. UMN MapServer can be compiled with this functionality and can then retrieve maps using its native protocols or GetMap (Figure 5-2).

Figure 5-2 The middleware GIS components of DISPRO.

The GIS client does not display a fixed set of layers. Rather, the system is dynamic, as the content presented in the GIS being dependent on the particular profile that is chosen by the user. A profile is simply a query to the catalogue encoded as a HTTP request. As such, it can be bookmarked in the browser for future re-use without having to complete a profile form again. For example, the following profile is a request to populate the GIS client with all those layers from four groups (base, emergency, marine, sensitive) which intersect a geographic bounding box of minX=46065.8, minY=20438.9, maxX=119947, maxY=60026.5, and are available in a projection of EPSG:29900.

```

http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dispro/disproquery.xml?minx=46065.8&miny=20438.9&max
x=119947&maxy=60026.5&bbox_button=submit&base=base&emergency=emergency&marine=
marine&sensitive=sensitive&epsg=EPSG:29900
  
```

The result set returned from the catalogue in response to the query is the set of all layers that satisfy the query requirements. As this is in XML format, its content can be extracted using XSLT for use in other files. DISPRO relies on the Apache Cocoon [ACP05] XML publishing framework (a Java application) which runs in the Apache Jakarta Tomcat [ASF05b] servlet container to effect these transformations.

The application of the XSLT stylesheet to the result set of layers produces three separate files which are required for UMN MapServer: a 'bookmark' file in HTML which sets up some initial parameters for the GIS client, and is bookmarkable, allowing the user to save the profile; a 'template' file in HTML which defines the interface of the GIS client, including the list of map layers available; a 'map file' which is the core configuration file of UMN MapServer, providing information and metadata on the map layers available.

Once these three files are generated and stored on the portal server in the appropriate locations for MapServer, the web browser is automatically directed to the URL of the 'bookmark' file. This file is a simple page providing a forward link to the web GIS interface, i.e., the 'template' file.

5.4 OGC WMS Integration

The portal catalogue is responsible for integrating the DISPRO WMS system (Figure 5-3). An aggregator continually retrieves the most current capabilities files from the participating nodes and stores them in the catalogue database. All the web-based applications (e.g. metadata query, profiler, bookmarker, web browser GIS client) available to the end user are based on queries to the catalogue. The browser GIS interface, in turn, interacts with the web GIS and WMS client components on the server to retrieve maps from various WMS nodes using the GetMap request and present them in the browser GIS interface.

Figure 5-3 DISPRO implements an OGC compliant WMS system.

5.5 DISPRO Applications

5.5.1 The Profiler

The profile form (Figure 5-4) (http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dispro/bbox-and-layers_query.xml) is generated automatically by a query to the catalogue. This form allows the user to set preferences for how the browser GIS client will be populated with data by setting the layer groups, geographic bounding box and map projection of interest. Once the form is submitted it returns a bookmarkable page which links directly to the GIS client.

As the profile form is designed for the expert user who understands geographic bounding boxes and spatial reference systems, a simpler interface is available for other non-specialist users. This can be just an ordinary (if lengthy) URL link on a web page (see section 5.3 for an example). Alternatively, as used for the regional demonstrations in DISMAR, a bookmark can be linked to a particular area of an imagemap (Figure 5-5). Clicking on a "hotspot" demarcated map region, e.g. "North Sea / Skagerrak" loads the browser GIS client with the profile bookmarked for that region. The map layers in the profile will be sourced from any OGC WMS compliant server registered with the DISPRO portal and having data satisfying that particular profile requirements (i.e. bounding box, projection, layer groups). The GIS client interface is built to W3C standards and uses XHTML [W3C05b], CSS [W3C05a] and ECMAScript (JavaScript) [ECMA92]. As such it should run in any modern browser and, because it does not rely on any other plug-in technologies, it is known as a "thin" client.

In the North Sea/Skagerrak example (Figure 5-6), the map layers are derived from the WMS server nodes at NERSC (MERIS images, gridlines), Met.no (wind, magnitude wind), NIVA (Ferrybox data) and PML (MODIS images, coastline).

DISPRO User Profile Form

Dispro allows you to set one or more profiles defined by geographic area, map projection and map layer groups of interest. Once created, a profile can be bookmarked in the browser for future fast access. To create a profile, complete the form below by providing bounding box values, an associated SRS, and one or more layer groups (maximum 10) and then click the submit button.

Please be aware that this tool is aimed at the expert user. Only certain combinations of bounding box, SRS, and layer groups will return data (depending on what is currently in the continually updated portal database). Non-expert users are advised to use the preset demonstration profiles [here](#).

Bounding Box	Spatial Reference System	Layer Groups
minX <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42001	<input type="checkbox"/> algae
minY <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42002	<input type="checkbox"/> base
maxX <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42003	<input type="checkbox"/> DNMI-ec_1
maxY <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42004	<input type="checkbox"/> DNMI-ec_2
<input type="button" value="submit"/>	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42400	<input type="checkbox"/> DNMI-Skag_1
DISPRO Home	<input type="radio"/> AUTO:42401	<input type="checkbox"/> DNMI-Skag_2
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:29900	<input type="checkbox"/> emergency
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:31463	<input type="checkbox"/> gb2sea00_1
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:32632	<input type="checkbox"/> marine
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:32633	<input type="checkbox"/> oil
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:32634	<input type="checkbox"/> sensitive
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:32635	
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:4267	
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:4269	
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:4326	
	<input type="radio"/> EPSG:9810	
	<input type="radio"/> Mercator WG584	

Figure 5-4 The DISPRO user profile form.

Figure 5-5 Demonstration regions bookmarked through an imagemap.

5.5.2 GIS Browser Client Interface

The GIS browser client interface (Figure 5-6) provides basic functions expected of a thin client such as selection/deselection of layers, drag-select zoom box, panning, zooming and centring, and reference map area and scalebar. It consists of four main areas: the map area, the layer list, the map controls, and the information panel. Most of the screen is occupied by the map. Eight directional arrows surrounding the map allow panning. Drag selecting (clicking on the map with the left mouse button and dragging to define a bounding box) allows the user to zoom in on an area.

The layer list lies to the right of the map. Layers are grouped under categories (e.g. base, marine, emergency, sensitive, oil, algae, met-ocean). Layers are selected for display by clicking in the selection box to the left of the layer name, and then clicking on the "refresh map" button beneath. This causes the portal application to issue a request (GetMap) to the relevant node(s). The returned raster maps are merged by the portal GIS application and presented in the client. Clicking on the layer name itself opens a separate browser window that displays the full discovery metadata file for that layer. The metadata file can include a link to download the actual data if the provider has made it available.

The controls section beneath the layer list allows the user to pan and zoom (in and out), and to set the zoom factor (the default is 2). The user first selects a zoom function and zoom factor, or the pan function, and then clicks on the map: the point clicked becomes the centre of the new map that is returned. The reference box and scalebar lie above the controls on the right of the screen. As the user zooms in on an area, a bounding box is drawn on the reference box to indicate the position of the new area relative to the full map area. The reference box is "clickable": clicking on a point on the reference box results in a new map with the bounding box centred on that point. The scalebar adjusts automatically to display the correct scale for each map that is returned.

Figure 5-6 The GIS client interface: North Sea / Skagerrak region; the four main areas of the client are evident: main map, layer list, controls and information panel; the latter is set to display the Updates utility.

The information panel lies beneath the main map. It allows the user to quickly access various information services by clicking on one of the tabs listed along the top of the panel: Intro, Updates, News, Notes, and Summary. Three are functional in DISPRO. Updates (Figure 5-6) displays the ten most recently added layers in descending chronological order, each item providing title, source and brief description. News (Figure 5-7) displays a news feed from the JRC European Media Monitor [JRC05]; this is a continually updated news stream that can be configured server-side to use filter terms relevant to DISMAR (e.g. oil spill, algal bloom, pollution, shipping hazard, etc.) thereby presenting the user with news items tailored to their area of interest. Notes (Figure 5-8) displays a brief comment/ interpretation note per layer, and, if available, a legend; the user simply moves the mouse over a layer name in the layer list to display this information.

Figure 5-7 The GIS client interface: the information panel is set to display a JRC European Media Monitor news feed.

Figure 5-8 The GIS client interface: the information panel is set to display an interpretation note (in this case for layer named "Habitats"); note legend graphic.

5.5.3 Metadata Query

Each data set in DISPRO has a companion metadata file which is stored locally on the node with the parent data set. In addition, a metadata abstract with a reduced number of entities, derived from the capabilities files, is stored in the catalogue on the portal. The catalogue search interface (Figure 5-9) is accessed by clicking on the "metadata database" link under "applications" on the DISPRO home page (<http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dismar/index.xml>). The user queries the database by selecting an element from a drop-down list and then entering a search term for that element. A boolean operator (and/or) function is available so search terms can be used in various combinations. A search may include a bounding box to limit the results to a geographic area of interest.

The results of a query are presented in a navigable list consisting of a summary of each data item that matches the search terms, with a link to the full metadata file transformed on-the-fly from XML to HTML.

Metadata Abstracts Catalogue Powered by eXist

element	operator	search term	BBox
Title	or	bathymetry	minX: -12 minY: 51 maxX: -10 maxY: 52
Title		conservation	

Submit Query

the Catalogue

1. Select an element from the element list.
2. Type the search term for that element.
3. Select the Boolean operator (and/or) if required.
4. Repeat steps 1 and 2, if required, for a second element.

The search term field uses free text searching; terms are case insensitive.

Use the wildcard * to replace one or more characters.

Use the wildcard ? to replace a single character.

Provide character ranges using [a-zA-Z].

[Dispro Home](#)

Figure 5-9 The query interface to the metadata catalogue; the user is looking for data items that intersect a bounding box of -12, 51, -10, 52 and whose title includes the term "bathymetry" or "conservation".

5.5.4 The OGC Web Map Servers

The WMS client on the portal communicates with one or more distributed OGC compliant WMS servers. There are eight WMS servers in the DISPRO network (Table 5-1). Other third party OGC WMS servers may be included by adding their capabilities URL to the aggregator. All but two of the DISPRO nodes use UMN MapServer, the exceptions being NIVA and Met.no, which use, respectively, ArcIMS and an in-house developed system. A particular demonstration region will feature data derived

from one or more of these servers (nodes). For example, the Skagerrak region demonstration contains inputs from nodes 5, 6, 7, and 8.

Table 5-1 OGC WMS server nodes in the DISPRO network.

	WMS Node	Service Description
1	CMRC	The CMRC is a supplementary DISPRO node not directly involved in a demonstration case. It is primarily used to prototype and test the set up of OGC web map services, and also to demonstrate how a rich set of GIS layers can enhance and provide context for the kinds of data generated by the specialist DISMAR data providers. This is especially important as many of the DISPRO nodes, for various reasons, have difficulties obtaining base data layers for their area.
2	GKSS	GKSS, in collaboration with two other data providing partners (OPTIMARE, RUB) is responsible for the DISPRO node covering the German Bight. This node demonstrates the integration and display of a variety of data sources including remote sensing (aircraft, satellites, ground based radar). All data providers deliver their products (maps, images, metadata, etc) via FTP to the German WMS. RUB delivers and receives radar maps for data fusion via FTP.
3	lfremer	The Ifremer node is concentrating on the Prestige oil spill case. It makes available a range of geo-referenced images covering the Prestige area derived from browsing hindcast model outputs and imagery, together with base maps for context. The data are provided by Cedre, Météo-France, Mercator, and Met.no. Work flow is manual. The node uses a static map file.
4	Met.no	The met.no node specialises in oil spill fate forecasting and algae forecasting, in support of real-time oil spill and HAB monitoring demos, respectively. The node also supplies forecast fields of relevant marine environmental parameters from numerical ocean models - ocean currents, temperature, salinity, algae and nutrient concentrations - as well as numerical weather predictions (NWP) such as wind, pressure, temperature, precipitation and surface waves. For DISPRO, the aim is to test the feasibility of daily algae forecasts and oil drift prognoses on request. The area of interest for the demo is the North Sea and Skagerrak, but NWP are available within met.no's area of interest (northern Europe). Ocean forecast and NWP layers are now available as OGC WMS layers, with prognoses of oil drift available for testing in DISPRO 2. Oil drift will, once in operational mode, be updated on request using a web order form. NWP are updated four times a day, the ocean forecasts once a day. Ocean forecasts and NWP are uploaded to the OGC WMS server as part of met.no's post processing routines. GetCapabilities are static map files.
5	NERSC	The NERSC DISPRO Node serves satellite data and derived products generated by NERSC during the second demonstration phase of DISMAR, i.e. during spring, summer and autumn of 2005. The node delivers various types of satellite data (SAR, optical) and derived products (oil spill analysis, chlorophyll-a concentrations, algal bloom interpretations), as well as sample base layers (coastline, bathymetry, gridlines). Each data set or product is accompanied by metadata in XML format (conforming to the DISPRO profile of ISO 19115), which is available through an HTTP web server on the DISPRO node. For data preparation and upload, satellite images are pre-processed and analysed by ESA, COTS and in-house developed software. Resulting images and analyses are prepared as files that can be handled by the UMN MapServer, typically TIFF for raster data and Shapefiles for vector data. Interpretations are provided as ASCII text, which is displayed in the "Notes" field of the DISPRO web portal.
6	NIVA	The main function of the NIVA node is to present FerryBox data from the Skagerrak with parameters to show algal blooms and water quality. FerryBox data consists of a number of parameters collected from sensors on board the ferry and transferred in real time to NIVA over the internet. Realtime functionality was not implemented in DISPRO 1. Data from water samples collected at fixed intervals or during HAB situations are analysed in the laboratory. These results can be shown together with the on board measurements. For the demo, NIVA node also provides a layer for aquaculture sites operated by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries. For the demonstration, in spring 2004, representative data for algal blooms were selected from the FerryBox database and converted to shapefiles for serving by the NIVA OGC WMS server. Metadata is prepared manually. Realtime functionality for Ferrybox data is implemented in DISPRO-2. The option to display MERIS satellite images as GeoTiff is implemented in DISPRO-2.
7	TSPZ	The Italian Node of DISPRO hosts vector layers of products derived from raster layers analysis, they are: oil spill detection, oil spill drift prediction (after 6, 12, 18 and 14 hours, produced by using the Università del Piemonte (UNIPM) Oil Drift Model) and algae detection. Moreover, it hosts several quicklook images from ASAR, Landsat and MERIS. The quicklook images of the raster layers from which the products are derived are also served. Vector data are served in shapefile format and raster data in TIFF format (with associated TIFF World File). Each data set or product is accompanied by metadata in text/xml format (conforming to the DISPRO profile in line with ISO19115), which is also served by the same web server.
8	PML	The PML node mainly serves gridded (raster) datasets. The focus is on near-real time (same day) automatic updating of satellite remotely sensed data on ocean colour (algae blooms) from NASA-MODIS and ESA-MERIS, and sea-surface temperature from NOAA-AVHRR. In addition model fields for four parameters are produced as a seven-day hindcast. Data preparation consists of converting datasets into GeoTIFF, then storing them on the web server. Unique in DISMAR, information about the data is registered in a database and the metadata are generated dynamically on request. Map files are dynamically generated based on the client request to the WMS.

6 Demonstration and validation

6.1 Overview of demonstration areas

The overall objective of DISMAR has been to develop an advanced information system for monitoring and forecasting the marine environment to improve management of pollution crises in coastal and ocean regions of Europe, in support of public administrations and emergency services responsible for prevention, mitigation and recovery of crises such as oil spill pollution and harmful algae blooms (HABs). In the third year of the project, we have developed the second version of a prototype information system, DISPRO-2.

The design and implementation of this prototype is based on the first version prototype DISPRO-1, which was developed during the first two years of the project. DISPRO-1 was developed on the basis of user requirements extracted from a survey of existing monitoring services in the participating countries (Norway, Germany, Italy, France, UK, Ireland), complemented with a literature review of recent coastal zone GIS for environmental monitoring, forecasting and risk management. The implementation is based on state-of-the-art GIS and web technologies, in line with recommendations from INSPIRE² and GMES³.

DISPRO-1 was demonstrated (DEMO-1) in five coastal zone and ocean areas in Europe where Web Map Servers have been installed: (1) North Sea / Skagerrak area, (2) coast of Germany, (3) coast of Italy, (4) coast of France and (5) south-western English Channel; an existing installation for Bantry Bay (Ireland) served as a reference (see Figure 6-1). Selected users in each demonstration area were involved in testing and evaluation of the distributed system. The following sections present a summary of the demonstrations in each region (sections 6.2-06.6), a synthesis of user feedback from all regions (section 6.7), and overall conclusions and recommendations (section 6.8). See [HH05a] for details on the first demonstration and validation of DISPRO-1, and [HH05b] for details on the demonstration and validation of DISPRO-2. See [OTu05] for a full description of the development of DISPRO-2.

Figure 6-1 The DISPRO-2 portal providing access to EO and in situ data, derived products and model forecasts in each of the indicated demonstration areas. The portal is available online at <http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dismar/index.xml>.

² <http://inspire.jrc.it/>

³ <http://www.gmes.info/>

6.2 North Sea/Skagerrak

In the North Sea and Skagerrak areas, marine crisis applications addressing both oil spill and harmful algal blooms have been demonstrated. The participating partners were: met.no, NERSC, NIVA and PML (HAB only). The information contributions and data flow are shown in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2 Data flow for DEMO-2 in the North Sea / Skagerrak area.

In the first demonstration, which was performed in year two of the project, the aim was to demonstrate the functionality and capabilities of the DISPRO-1 system as a tool for monitoring and managing oil spill and HAB incidents, and to recommend revisions to DISPRO based on critique from the users. The DEMO-1 pair of demonstrations aimed to test a static WMS system, i.e., a hindcast test case, making maximal use of *existing* data products. Consequently, all access to the system was restricted to partners and selected users. DEMO-1 was assessed by DISMAR team members and colleagues at the participating institutes with respect to the overall concept and basic functionalities. The critique and recommendations from this assessment were analysed and a number of priority developments were identified for the second stage prototype service, DISPRO-2, which was demonstrated in the second demonstration DEMO-2.

In DEMO-2, the aim was to simulate a real crisis situation, i.e., a real-time exercise making maximal use of available observational and model information. DEMO-2 was performed at the end of the project period using the upgraded prototype web service DISPRO-2.

6.2.1 Oil spill case

The North Sea and Skagerrak are heavily trafficked by different types of vessels, and a significant number of operational oil installations are placed there. There have been many observations of oil spills in the last few years, originating from ship traffic or the oil industry. Detection, monitoring and forecasting are essential components in a oil spill crisis management system. Detection and monitoring were exemplified with Envisat ASAR data, provided by NERSC (cf. Section 3.3), since this is one type of satellite imagery that will be an important data source in a future operational DISPRO system as well as in other monitoring and forecasting systems operating under the context of GMES. Model forecasts of oil drift and environmental conditions (wind, waves, currents), provided by met.no (cf. Section 3.9), were the other important information element in oil spill emergency management. These data were made available as web map layers on the respective partners' servers. Base layers included coastline and fish farm locations, provided by NERSC and NIVA.

For DEMO-1 purposes, it was sufficient to provide typical ASAR images and model simulation renderings independent of real oil spill occurrences. Sample ASAR images showing oil slicks were

selected from archives, processed as for oil detection, and then supplied to the NERSC node along with basic metadata. A number of sample model products, primarily 2-dimensional fields of surface currents, temperature, salinity, winds and waves, from met.no's operational models were rendered as contour or vector plots on the met.no node. The data layers were successfully accessed by the DISPRO server and displayed on the DISPRO web client (see Figure 6-3).

Figure 6-3 Screen shot of DISPRO-1 showing combination of satellite observation and model forecast data appropriate for oil spill monitoring and response. Shown are two ASAR images and model prognoses for 10m winds (arrows) and significant wave height (contours). The lower ASAR image has a slick signature off the west coast of Denmark (marked with a red circle).

Assessment of the oil spill case in DEMO-1 indicated that the DISPRO-1 was promising but required significant improvements, including: (1) offer better handling of time series, such as model forecasts and series of satellite images, (2) restriction of model parameters shown to those relevant to oil spill/HAB monitoring, (3) more base layers (e.g. higher resolution coastline, bathymetry), and (4) shorter access time.

Based on the assessment, a number of developments were carried out for DISPRO-2. A targeted set of ASAR images covering the northern North Sea was acquired and made available on the NERSC node. It was not, however, feasible to acquire suitably processed ASAR images in near-real-time for the second demonstration. The oil spill forecast system was implemented as an end-to-end web service. This entailed building the web-based order form (Figure 3-25) and making it accessible to users, completing and verifying the modularisation of the code, and enhancing the rendering of oil variables on the met.no node. The menus and layer groupings were revised in order to make it easier to find the most relevant layers. The selection of geophysical data layers from forecast models was revised. Several base layers were added, including coastlines, bathymetry, fish farm locations and aquaculture license sites. In addition, data layers targeted for the HAB application, such as satellite chlorophyll concentration images and ecosystem model forecasts, were made accessible together with oil spill layers. Figure 6-4 shows an example of a simulated oil spill along with other relevant information layers.

6.2.2 HAB case

The ichthyotoxic flagellate *Chattonella* aff. *verriculosa* appears to have established itself in the Skagerrak after an initial harmful bloom in March 1998. Blooms have occurred in successive springs with varying toxic impact on fish, depending mainly on the circulation pattern. In 2005 only low cell numbers of this species was registered. Other harmful species like the flagellated form of *Dictyocha speculum* have occurred in moderate concentrations in spring and early summer. In the middle of August 2005 there was a small bloom of *Karenia mikimotoi* (syn. *Gyrodinium aureolum*), but it culminated after a couple of weeks. Day-to-day monitoring of algal concentration and species composition, along with model forecasts are key elements in a HAB crisis management service. In DISMAR, monitoring information includes satellite ocean colour imagery from MODIS and MERIS supplied by NERSC and PML, and Ferrybox observations along the Oslo-Hirtshals route provided by

NIVA. Daily model forecasts of nutrient and phytoplankton concentrations were provided by met.no. These data were made available as web map layers on the respective partners' servers. Base layers included coastline and fish farm locations, provided by NERSC, NIVA and PML.

For DEMO-1, various representative data layers were included: MODIS images showing derived chlorophyll-A; Ferrybox observations of along-track temperature, salinity, turbidity, chlorophyll-a fluorescence and algal concentration; model forecast fields of surface nutrients and phytoplankton, as well as surface currents, temperature, salinity, winds and waves, rendered as contour or vector plots on the met.no node. The data layers were successfully accessed by the DISPRO server and displayed on the DISPRO web client (see Figure 6-5).

For the second HAB demonstration, near-real time monitoring and forecasting of algal concentrations were in focus. Developments for DISPRO-2 included: near-real-time access to Ferrybox data from NIVA; an expert evaluation of the current algae situation from NIVA, available as metadata; adding MERIS ocean colour data from NERSC; a routine weekly composite MODIS ocean colour image from PML; a full range of model forecast fields (surface currents, temperature, salinity, weather, waves) from met.no; access to the same base layers as the oil spill case. An example of the DISPRO-2 content is shown in Figure 6-6.

Figure 6-4 Screen shot of DISPRO-2 showing data from met.no's operational oil drift, ocean and weather forecast models. Shown is a simulated oil slick (surface oil concentration as grey shading and oil drift velocity as blue arrows), 2m air temperature as green contours and surface current as red arrows, along with a coastline base layer and an aquaculture site base layer (blue dots).

Figure 6-5 Screen shots of DISPRO during DEMO-1. Left: Chlorophyll-a derived from MODIS data. Acquisition date is 2 June 2004. Right: Chlorophyll fluorescence measured by the Ferrybox sensor installed on the ColorLine ferry running between Oslo and Hirtshals, a set of water samples collected in the North Sea, and fish farms located on the coast and in the fjords of southern Norway.

Figure 6-6 Screen shot of DISPRO-2 showing example of combining different data layers to elucidate the algae situation in the Skagerrak. Included are chlorophyll fluorescence observations from the Oslo-Hirtshals Ferrybox and MODIS weekly composite (grey tones), observed algae from water samples, together with model forecasts of surface current (red arrows) and flagellate concentration (blue contours). Also shown are fish farm locations (blue dots).

6.2.3 User feedback from the demonstrations

Assessments of the North Sea / Skagerrak demonstrations were similar for the oil spill and HAB cases, and are summarised in a few positive and negative points.

- + The main strength of DISPRO is the ability to gather and combine diverse information layers from different, distributed sources. For example, users admired the ability to view static information such as aquaculture sites along with dynamic layers like satellite imagery and in situ measurements of chlorophyll; and they asked for more base layers.
- + Map based presentation of data and information layers is an appealing way of presenting both an oil spill response service and an algae bloom monitoring and forecasting service. Providing access to the system through in a web browser means that the user is already familiar with the user interface and how to operate it. That no special plug-ins or other software had to be installed to access and display the products was considered a positive feature.
- + Obtaining access to *coincident* data from all sources (i.e. observations, derivations and predictions) is considered crucial for efficient HAB monitoring. Important parameters, like chlorophyll-a (both derived and predicted), SST, currents, wind and waves, are available in DISPRO. Especially, for DEMO-2, users were pleased with finding a good diversity of information layers available.
- + A major weakness is the presentation of time series. This particularly problematic for the oil spill case, where forecasts are a vital tool for decision-making. In a crisis situation, the user requires quick and intuitive access to the time evolution of the oil slick. The WMS standard [OGC04] allows a time coordinate to be specified for each layer, but the WMS tool used to implement DISPRO, the University of Minnesota Map Server [UMN05], does not support this parameter. Thus, only work-around solutions could be implemented for DISPRO-2.
- + DISPRO-1 was considered to be "slow" by some users, but response time improved in the second version of the prototype when a dedicated server was set up for DISPRO-2. A more critical performance related issue was that, in some cases, certain layers were not displayed. This may happen due to network problems (e.g. connection timeout) or DISPRO nodes being temporarily unavailable (e.g. due to maintenance). Regardless of reason, DISPRO should have given an informative error message. In a prototype, variable performance is acceptable, but for an operational system performance and reliability are key factors to its success.

6.3 Coast of Germany

6.3.1 Introduction

The German Bight and especially the port of Hamburg are attracting an increasing amount of ship traffic. As a consequence the risk of an accident and thus of an oil pollution is increasing as well. The scenario assumed for the first and the second demonstration was: "An illegal release of oil has occurred approximately 10 nm west of the Schleswig-Holstein coastline (North Germany). During westerly winds the harbour of Buesum and its vicinity is threatened by the drifting oil."

The aim of the German demonstration was to demonstrate the functionality and capabilities of the DISPRO system as a tool for monitoring and managing the oil spill incident and to assess the value of the system based on response from the users.

Optimare, GKSS and RUB were involved in the German demonstration.

6.3.2 Observations

Radar imagery is capable of detecting oil spills, biogenic slicks and certain hydrodynamic effects that are associated with a reduction in surface roughness. Radar imagery acquired by side-looking airborne radar (SLAR), X-band coastal radar (land-/ship-based Doppler radar) and satellite-based SAR were used to demonstrate the capabilities of DISPRO. The corresponding demo experiment is based on a fictive scenario because the possibilities of performing experimental releases of oil to the sea are very limited. Concerning the use of airborne, satellite-based and land-/ship-based Doppler observation systems in this demonstration, basic features of radar imagery caused by spilled oil have to be replaced within the area of interest by similar radar features caused by different ocean phenomena. Examples are slicks of surface-active biogenic material and/or hydrodynamic effects which both may reduce the radar backscattering cross-section. Such phenomena that always represent potential false targets in radar-based oil spill remote sensing are known to occur especially in the Meldorf Bight area (Figure 6-7, southernmost demonstration area). They served as substitutes for radar signatures caused by spilled oil during the second German Bight demonstration.

Figure 6-7 Demo areas in the German Bight: Sylt (northernmost area), Meldorf Bight (southernmost area). The 2nd demo was carried out in the Meldorf Bight area.

6.3.3 Observations Products

The demonstrations were based on the observation products (data layers) mentioned below:

- **Side-looking Airborne Radar (SLAR) data.** Supplied by OPTIMARE as PNG+WORLD files and provided to the user as web map layers from the GKSS DISPRO node (Figure 6-8)
- **Land- and ship-based X-band radar data.** Supplied by GKSS as PNG+WORLD files and provided to the user as web map layers from the GKSS DISPRO node (Figure 6-9) and
- **Satellite SAR data.** Envisat ASAR (APP mode) and ERS-2 data (low resolution) supplied by RUB as TIFF+WORLD files and provided to the user as web map layers from the GKSS DISPRO node (Figure 6-10)

The data and the corresponding metadata were integrated in the DISPRO system. The functionalities of the DISPRO system were demonstrated twice to the Central Command for Maritime Emergencies Germany (CCME).

According to the CCME, the DISPRO system features an intuitive and clear layout, clear instructions and descriptions, and is easy to handle. Apart from firewall-related problems causing a substantial slowdown of the Internet access to DISPRO, the overall rating of DISPRO by CCME was good. However, an indication of time of the displayed layers should be added to the map, as should a scale bar and coordinate extraction facility. The ability to serve data over low bandwidth is particularly important for users onboard vessels, where the connection speed is low compared to land-based networks. This was also pointed out as a feature that should be taken into consideration when enhancing the system. In the context of oil spill response in the German Bight. CCME also suggested the following improvements to advance DISPRO towards an pre-operational GMES service: (1) rapid transfer of remote sensing data from the German maritime surveillance aircraft to the ground station, and (2) integration of remote sensing data in the ECDIS system (Electronic Chart Display and Information System).

Figure 6-8 Example of aircraft data (SLAR) on the German Web Map Server. The data were acquired by the German maritime surveillance aircraft 57+01 (LM1) over the demo site 'Buesum' and processed by OPTIMARE.

Figure 6-9 Example of coastal and ship radar maps (X-band) on the German Web Map Server. The data were acquired and processed by GKSS.

Figure 6-10 Screenshot of the Web Map Server Interface showing a fragment of ENVISAT ASAR oil spill image provided by RUB.

6.4 Coast of France

On November 13, 2002 the tanker Prestige provoked the third major oil spill in Galicia in less than 30 years and also the third spill of heavy oil in Europe in less than 4 years after those of Erika (1999) and Baltic Carrier (2001). This shows that the risk remains very high all over the area going from the Atlantic approaches to North-West Europe into the Channel, North Sea and the Baltic.

Along with the Spanish authorities directly concerned with the spill, the French anti-pollution response mechanism was immediately set up, with a view to a) assist the Spanish authorities, b) forecast the spill drift and get prepared to a likely impact to the Spanish and French coasts. Responsibilities for safety and rescue at sea in France are shared by CROSS (French MRCC), Préfets Maritimes (PREMAR) and SNSM (the French Life Boat Association), while responsibilities for pollution response are with the Customs, the Préfet Maritime and *Cedre*. A Centre of Operations was immediately set up at the Préfecture Maritime and a daily meeting was held with all the parties involved. All related data were collated on a daily basis and synthesized by *Cedre* in a GIS and used at the meeting for subsequent decisions.

From the day of the wreckage of the Prestige (19 November, 2002), *Cedre* published daily charts (week-ends and public holidays included) about all the observed pollution at sea and included drift prediction (Figure 6-11). These charts became an efficient communication tool between all the actors, being in France or in Spain. They were sent to response teams on sites and to all relevant authorities every evening and to the general public two days later (Internet in static form – jpeg format). These charts have progressively included complementary information: type of pollution, surveillance flight plans, MOTHY model forecast, drifting buoys successive positions, oil impacted shorelines. From the beginning of the spill, a « drift committee » met every evening to build up these charts, to validate and publish this data synthesis.

Unfortunately, the data were not digitalised and had to be manually inserted into the database of the GIS used to generate the synthesis maps. The input operation was a time consuming task, especially when it includes hundreds of slick observations. The first demonstration for French users thus focused on the Prestige accident, trying to integrate multiple data sources in a single system, DISPRO-1. This demonstration included data from, among others: (1) ENVISAT ASAR images, (2) aerial, terrestrial, vessel based observations in the whole period, (3) coastline and bathymetry, (5) EEZ and terrestrial sea limits, and (6) forecasts of oil spill drift from two providers, met.no and Météo-France. Figure 6-12 shows some of the layers from this demonstration displayed in DISPRO-1.

Figure 6-11 Synthesis Map realized during the Prestige accident.

Figure 6-12 Screen shot of the DISPRO-1 interface showing a selection of available layers. Shown are base layers (coastline, bathymetry), information on the Prestige tow route, oil slick information from visual observations and the met.no oil drift model, SAR imagery and aircraft surveillance areas.

The Prestige hindcast study was presented both internally at *Cedre* and for PREMAR. The concept of getting access to all needed data in a single system was well received. However, as this was the first version of the prototype, several suggestions for improvements were given. For instance, that the menu organisation and navigation should be made more intuitive and user friendly. The ability to get the data files of selected layers for further processing in local systems was desired; a download option was in place but not all providers made the underlying data available. Finally, in an operational system agreements must be set up with providers to ensure timely and reliable delivery of data, and it must be possible to restrict the access to certain types of products ensuring that only authorised personnel is granted access to sensitive information.

For the second demonstration, an area in the English Channel, North of the French Brittany region was chosen (Figure 6-13). The area is particularly exposed to oil spill risk because of an intense maritime traffic and strong tidal currents. The demo corresponds to a fictive accident of a ship called NIMBUS at position 049°00'00"N and 003°02'00"W on the January 10, 2004.

Figure 6-13 Demonstration area for the Coast of France.

This demonstration focused on showing forecasted oil drift from the (fictive) spill. Météo-France has developed MOTHY, an operational pollutant drift model that can be used 24h/24 for oil spills or drifting objects. MOTHY is an integrated system that includes hydrodynamic coastal ocean modelling and real time atmospheric forcing from a global or a limited area model. The hydrodynamic ocean model is linked to an oil spill model, where oil slick is considered as a distribution of independent droplets. These droplets move with shear current, turbulent diffusion and buoyancy. Figure 6-14 shows an example of a MOTHY forecast, with different colour coding of spill origin (black), 12 hour forecast (purple), 24 and 36 hour forecast (both red). Cedre also gets some aerial and terrestrial observations from the CROSS (Operational, Survey and Rescue Regional Center), the FRENCH NAVY and customs that are converted to important input data (Figure 6-15).

Figure 6-14 Example of MOTHY oil drift model representation after geocoding and analysis.

Figure 6-15 Screen shot from DISPRO-2 showing a selection of available layers. Shown are base layers (coastline), information on the ship route and an aircraft surveillance area.

6.5 Coast of Italy

The objective of the DISMAR demonstration over Italian waters has been to show users both utility and usability of the developed DISPRO system. This has been realized exploiting acquired archives data of both ERS and Envisat for what concerns oil spill, and acquired archives data of MERIS for what concerns mucilage, as well as some higher resolution data (Landsat).

The following DISMAR partners have been involved in the DISPRO demonstration for Italian waters:

- Telespazio, setting up the local node of the DISPRO system, providing layers related to the occurrence of mucilage and generating metadata related to all basic and thematic information within the repository of the Italian DISPRO local node
- ASI, providing SAR images and the related OSAD output on the presence of detected oil spills
- UNIPMN, providing the oil spill drifting as model output

The following users have been involved in both DEMO-1 and DEMO-2:

- Laboratorio di Biologia Marina - Provincia di Bari: a research institute involved in the analysis and monitoring of sea water for the evaluation of coastal environmental conditions. They are mainly interested in the information extracted by the satellite images
- Basilicata Regional Agency for the Environment (ARPAB): they are interested both in the information the system can provide and into the DISPRO exploited technologies (web based applications, GIS)

For the oil spill detection purposes, ERS/Envisat products, particularly Precision Resolution Images (PRIs) have been exploited, ingested into the OSAD system for the extraction of oil spill geographical position and related parameters. The output of the OSAD system has then been ingested into the repository being part of the Italian local DISPRO node, as well as into the oil spill drifting model of UNIPMN. The latter, also exploiting wind and current data compatible with a particular satellite acquisition produced the forecast of the oil spill drifting that has been ingested into the repository itself.

All layers ingested into the repository have been described by the related metadata according to the selected standard exploiting the XMLSpy editor. Metadata for the available layers have been uploaded to DISPRO-2 and can be retrieved by means of the search facility of the metadata catalogue.

All of the above information layers have been overlaid on context data, such as coastlines and administrative boundaries, which are also present into the repository.

The web map server used by Telespazio has been the University of Minnesota MapServer (version 4.4.1) [UMN05]. Data transfer to/from the local repository and Web Map Server has been based on the HTTP protocol.

After an analysis of last three years of the interventions made by the Ministry of Environment along the Italian coasts, the Italian Partners selected four areas of interest, which are particularly exposed to the oil spill risk because of an intense maritime traffic. These are the Sicily Channel, the southern and northern Tyrrhenian Sea and the southern Adriatic Sea (see Figure 6-16). The OSAD output is represented by a shapefile showing the contour of detected oil spills.

The main model output is the position and shape of the oil slick(s), delivered as a time series of text files, each one containing the slick contour at a fixed time after acquisition. The contour files are also converted to shapefiles in order to be distributed through the Italian Web Map Server. Every shapefile contains all slicks identified in a SAR image (see Figure 6-17).

Figure 6-16 The area selected for DEMO-2 with selected ENVISAT wide swath scenes.

Figure 6-17 Model output at different times exploiting available wind information.

The second part of the Italian Demo concentrated on detection of mucilage occurrence in Adriatic Sea, where such a phenomenon periodically occurs, mainly during summer time. Layers related to mucilage have been generated and ingested into the local repository of the DISPRO system and the related metadata have been produced, in order to let such information be available through the DISPRO web portal. Also context data (coastlines, main cities, etc.) has been made available. For the above purpose, MERIS data have been exploited, as well as Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 data, because of the better spatial resolution.

The general consensus of the users involved in the demo on both system capability and data provided has been expressed. Some suggestions have been provided for what concerns the portal layout and interfaces. The system has been found very useful for a general public or fish farmers, while it is less important for institutional end users, who would prefer to receive the relevant information also directly by other means (i.e. fax, SMS, etc.).

The information content has been found really interesting. It has been found also attractive to have access to other information extracted by satellite data as wind speed and direction, sea surface temperature, that are used in some of the application presented.

6.6 Western English Channel

6.6.1 Introduction

Blooms of the red-tide dinoflagellate *Karenia mikimotoi* (previously known as *Gyrodinium aureolum*) occur regularly during summer in the western English Channel (WEC) and appear as high chlorophyll on ocean colour images. The species has been associated with fish mortality, has an adverse effect on production of copepod eggs and in South Africa *Karenia cf mikimotoi* have been associated with human respiratory problems. Hence, this species represents a good example of a harmful algal bloom (HAB). Other blooms also occur during the Summer including the non-harmful coccolithophore *Emiliana huxleyi*: these have high reflectance signatures that mean they can be readily differentiated from other species and provide an alternative species for operational monitoring.

The first aim was to demonstrate the functionality and capabilities of the DISPRO system to potential users interested in detection, monitoring and management of harmful algal blooms (and associated water quality). The second aim was to recommend revisions to DISPRO-2 based on comments from the users. The original plan for DISPRO-2 was to show data purely for the WEC (see box in Figure 6-18(a)); however, in response to the review panel the demo region was extended to include the whole NW European shelf including the Norwegian HAB area and Ferrybox track in the Skagerrak.

6.6.2 Methods

DISPRO1 was operated during the Summer and Autumn 2004 and was evaluated by Dr Bill Turrell, Science Director of both the Marine Ecosystems Programme and the Fisheries Management Programme at the Fisheries Research Services, Marine Lab Aberdeen. (<http://www.marlab.ac.uk/>). The system was also demonstrated to representative from the UK Environment Agency, CEFAS, the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency and others (see [Z+04]). DISPRO1 continued operation until the start of DISPRO-2 so it was possible to demonstrate the system to visiting scientists.

For DISPRO-2 profiles were constructed that included the following data: PML provided satellite ocean colour and SST data in near-real time and as composites (see section 3.7) and model output as a seven day hindcast (section 3.11). Meteorological model over the whole region and algal model output (section 0) covering Norway and northern Scotland were provided by met.no. Ferrybox data were presented from NIVA and additional fields from IFREMER and CMRC were used to show other capabilities of the DISPRO-2 system. In addition, a standalone "Summer 2005" group was produced that showed the archived satellite and model data for the *K. mikimotoi* bloom (see Figure 6-18(a)).

DISPRO-2 was operated throughout 2005 but the key period was when the system was evaluated for a second time by Dr Turrell and by Dr David Cotton, project manager with Satellite Observing Systems, Ltd, and co-ordinator of UK involvement in ESA MarCoast GMES service element (Water Quality and Harmful Algal Blooms). In this role Dr Cotton has significant involvement with all UK agencies responsible for water quality monitoring. He is also programme manager of UK Marine Data Information Partnership (MDIP). User testing forms, including the quantitative evaluation forms, were completed and provided to the University of Nottingham. The system was also shown to Dr David Palmer, Head of Technology at the Environment Agency (EA). The EA is responsible for maintaining and improving marine and fresh water quality (<http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/>).

6.6.3 Results

The results presented herein comprise a synthesis of the users' experiences in using DISPRO -2. A thorough quantitative statistical analysis is presented in [HH05b] and section 6.7 below.

Overall feedback on DISPRO-2 was very positive, seen as a distinct improvement over DISPRO1 and definitely better than other existing systems. However, comments were less favourable on the "look and feel" that was considered to be rather old-fashioned and should have a "windows-like" feel, while the layout could be improved. Performance was rated well with users commenting that DISPRO-2 was impressively quick or with a good speed of response (in contrast to the earlier DISPRO-1). Users had little difficulty in navigating the system, though they were from physical-sciences background, and it was noted that the system would need a certain level of expertise for interpretation; however, in operation, training would be provided for DISPRO and specialist users would be the key target group.

Comments on the functionality were both positive and negative; most specific comments concerned how the system could be improved notably on how different layers could be discriminated (when displayed together) or compared (e.g. side-by-side) and how layer presentation could be improved (e.g. specification of model contour levels). In order to meet some of the user requirements, noted in the first demonstrations, on image contrast enhancement and colour-changing (features not possible in the WMS specification), a link was made between the layer metadata and the PML image browser. Users found this easy enough to use and generally like the linkages available in the metadata.

Arguably the key feedback was on the information content reflecting where considerable effort was expended in the project. Content was rated as "lower side of excellent" and completeness as "perhaps not all, but most for a general user" but the same user marked down the spatial data availability noting that some layers (e.g. POLCOMS model data west of Scotland) are not available: however, these data are available from an institute outside the DISMAR consortium. The metadata were considered to be a very positive and "very full" component. Spatial resolution of satellite images needed to be better for applications; however, the resolution required (down to metre-scale) at a high temporal frequency is impossible using current satellite data availability and, in any case, would be prohibitively expensive since most high-resolution satellites are operated commercially. The lack of palettes was felt to be a major absence (though these were switched off for the demonstrations due to firewall issues at some partner's sites). The richness of the information input had a disadvantage in that there are a lot of layers under a lot of groups, with quite complex lists to scroll through and it was felt that there was some ambiguity on where layers are located (e.g. Irish and Norwegian aquaculture sites were in different groups) and uncertainty as to where layers are located (e.g. algae forecast should be separated from the MetOcean data).

In terms of usefulness one user graded it "on lower side of extremely useful" and they could envisage using the system by combining images and water current model to give background and context of bloom and environmental monitoring. Also, it would be used to respond to fish farmers' concerns on HAB's. For many applications it was felt that a simplified system was needed that provided a go/no-go or red/green solution stating whether a problem needed addressing or not. Users noted that they would like to see a facility where, having chosen a number of rasters and vectors, they could click back or forward one day to see the same set of layers but for a different day.

6.6.4 Conclusion

Overall DISPRO-2 was well regarded and the quantitative analysis showed that the WEC was rated highest out of all the demonstrations. It is also gratifying that the users could envisage making use of the system for real applications. The system is also likely to provide a mode of data access to the PML observatory and will also form the basis of a prototype web-based GIS system in an EC Framework 6 INCO-DEV project (SPEAR).

Figure 6-18 (a) AVHRR SST composite for NW European shelf showing western English Channel in the overlaid white box. (b) DISPRO-2 screenshot of "Summer 2005" group showing MERIS and MODIS 7-day chl-a composites overlaid with modelled "K mikimotoi" concentration, and NIVA's Ferrybox chl-a & HAB determinations.

6.7 User testing and validation

6.7.1 Introduction

Various methods of user testing were performed throughout the development of DISPRO-2. Certain demonstration reports refer to general, ongoing in-house testing during development. However, in addition to various informal testing programmes, a generic end user testing procedure was implemented. Specifically, a formal user testing procedure was employed, whereby users carried out specified tasks and recorded their evaluation of various aspects of DISPRO-2 on proforma user testing forms.

6.7.2 User testing methodology

A six-stage user testing methodology was developed:

1. Awareness

It must first be ensured that the proposed user testing procedure is described well in advance and that the necessary time and commitment to user testing is given. It should be made clear that the use of this testing methodology will be mandatory and that all procedures and reporting will be followed carefully and in detail. Each site should nominate an 'observer' who will observe users at their desk conducting tasks in DISPRO and who will guide the 'data gathering' procedure.

2. Observation and task definition

User testing should normally commence with the observer observing users working informally with the system at their desks with a view to establishing an initial set of tasks that will help structure a formal user testing session.

3. User testing criteria

An important step is to identify criteria that can be used within an evaluation procedure (indicated in table a below). The mode of data collection will also allow free format responses to gather ad-hoc qualitative information that may be valuable in the final reporting procedure.

4. User testing methodology

Ideally the observer should arrange with the user a time (at least an hour) to sit with them at their desk to record information about how the user interacts with the system and how successfully tasks are carried out. The observer should explain the purpose of the user testing procedure, introduce the initial set of tasks and ask the user to begin to work through the tasks in turn. Users should be asked to 'think out loud' to enable the facilitator to make notes on the users thought processes which may reveal important issues not covered explicitly by the evaluation metrics.

5. Data analysis

All paper records of the user sessions should be copied locally and copies returned for data analysis and reporting centrally. The coded responses in the evaluation metrics table will be integrated with qualitative information from the notes made by observer and user in the form of a report. The overall intention is to summarise responses against evaluation criteria, task list and user expertise/domain knowledge.

6. Report and presentation

Results will be disseminated via report, presentation and discussion based on:

- Observed task structure across all sites (generic and specific tasks).
- Summaries of evaluation metrics.
- Implications for fine tuning of system design interface design.
- Implications for data or functionality.

6.7.3 User testing results

The main empirical element of the user testing form was the table of evaluation metrics. These enabled users to rate the various components of the DISPRO-2 system with clear numerical scores. The full data set of evaluation metrics is presented in Table 6-1, along with summary statistics. The

users are listed in columns, categorized according to country and the type of marine pollution of interest. The shaded cells represent original data values extracted from the returned forms, while the unshaded rows and column represent total values, summed by user or category. The evaluation scores (cell values) range from -1 to 1, whereby -1 = unsatisfactory, 0 = acceptable and 1 = good.

Table 6-1 User testing - summary of criteria and evaluation metrics.

	Norway			Ger- many	France		Italy		UK		Total
	SFT	FHL	FD	CCMA	Cedre 1	Cedre 2	LBM	ARPAB	MLA	SOS	
Oil spill	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Harmful algal bloom	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	
Usability											
Layout	0	-1	0	1	-1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Data Access	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Functionality	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	-2
Task Achievement	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	1	0	1	1	1
Usability total	0	-2	0	2	-2	-2	1	0	1	2	0
Technology											
Speed	0	0	0	-1	1	0	0	-1	0	1	0
Technology total	0	0	0	-1	1	0	0	-1	0	1	0
Base Mapping											
Clarity	1	0	0	0	0	-1	0	1	1	1	3
Legend Support	0		-1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	-2
Completeness	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
Base Mapping total	1	-1	-1	0	0	-2	0	2	2	1	2
Further Content											
Spatial data	0	-1	1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1
Text	1	-1	0	1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0
Metadata	1	-1	0	1		1	-1	-1	1	0	1
Products	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	1		1	0	0
Updating	1		1	-1	0	0		0	1	1	3
Further Content total	3	-4	2	1	0	0	0	-2	2	1	3
Overview											
Usefulness	0	-1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	4
Alternative systems		1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	5
Value		-1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overview total	0	-1	3	0	0	0	2	1	2	2	9
Grand total	4	-8	4	2	-1	-4	3	0	7	7	14

6.7.4 Summary

Generic end user testing has enabled a rigorous investigation of the success of DISPRO-2 in meeting the needs of a wide range of user organisations. Ten users tested DISPRO-2, specifying and undertaking certain tasks of particular interest to them. The overall view is clearly positive, as demonstrated by the evaluation metrics and various supporting comments from the users. The overall sum evaluation metric score is 14 (table a), indicating a very favourable overall impression. However, it is clear that certain aspects of the system are stronger than others in meeting user needs. In particular, in terms of evaluation categories, while the 'overview' category was very positive, others (specifically, usability and technology) were less so. In fact, although no general 'categories' dropped below a score

of zero (acceptable), certain specific 'criteria' (i.e. functionality, legend support, spatial data) did drop below zero (unsatisfactory). The limitations of these criteria were further reinforced through user comments. It is clear that wider adoption and exploitation of a system like DISPRO-2 would be beneficial to a users requiring operational (real-time) information on marine pollution. However, the success of such a system will require certain refinements to ensure that sufficient information products are available to meet the needs of the wide range of users and that the system is fully intuitive and usable by all, including non-expert users.

6.8 Conclusions

DISPRO has been developed in the DISMAR project as a prototype information system aimed at supporting marine environmental emergency management. It employs emerging web technology – Web Mapping Services (WMS) – for integration and distribution of multi-source data and numerical model results from a distributed network of sensors. The technology is based on ISO, OGC and W3C standards, using Open Source software. For two emergency applications, marine oil spill and harmful algal blooms, the prototype has been applied and demonstrated in five diverse regions of the European seas.

While the evaluations in DEMO-1 were generally favourable, the users pointed out a number of deficiencies in the form and content of DISPRO-1, and requested enhanced or additional capabilities. These criticisms were systematically analysed and prioritised in the development of DISPRO-2. Most of the identified shortcomings and enhancements to DISPRO-1 were addressed, but some were deemed unfeasible within the project framework. [OTu05] gives a fuller description of the DISPRO-2 development, and the underlying technologies and tools used in the implementation, while [HOTu05] addresses aspects of data standardization and harmonization encountered, as well as summarising the experiences of the data providers setting up nodes supplying data to the system.

Overall, the user response to DISPRO-2 has been very positive. Nearly all users have commented that DISPRO has an easily grasped, easily used user-interface and that it has the potential of providing a useful tool for marine emergency monitoring and management. In particular, users who were involved in both the DEMO-1 and DEMO-2 evaluations were impressed by the improvements to the system in the latter demonstration. The primary strengths of DISPRO-2 may be summarized as follows:

1. The user-interface is simple and easy to grasp. The use of a uniform layout across all the regions in the portal makes it easy to familiarise from one region/application to another.
2. The ability to integrate diverse information from a variety of distributed sources is generally regarded by users as the distinguishing feature of DISPRO. Integration of data from multiple providers often has to be done manually by explicitly exporting, converting and importing data files.
3. Users were favourably impressed by the mix of information content available in the demonstration applications. A number of different data types and products were demonstrated, including, among others, satellite radar and ocean colour data, aircraft visible, infrared and microwave data, X-band radar data, Ferrybox measurements, met-ocean forecasts, oil spill drift forecasts, algae bloom evolution and spread predictions.
4. DISPRO-2 is shown to be well suited for assessing emergency management in retrospect, i.e., integrating diverse information available for a past incident. A good example is the "Prestige" oil spill demonstration case performed by the French team in DEMO-1.
5. Near-real-time monitoring is well provided for in DISPRO-2 through specifically developed products from the data providers. For instance, ocean colour and algae parameters from Ferrybox systems.

A further advantage was that all data and information could be accessed through a common web browser, with no need for plug-ins. On the other hand, the second demonstration phase, DEMO-2, also identified some remaining shortcomings:

1. The layer menu, while simple to learn, becomes unwieldy in use when there is a large number of layers to organise. Even if layers are grouped, scrolling through the layer list can be tedious, and it can be difficult to get an overview of available layers.
2. Time series are not handled well. (The WMS specification includes time coordinates for layers, but the tool used to implement DISPRO, the UMN MapServer [UMN05], does not support this parameter.)

3. There are limitations to how much information can be laid onto the map, and this can hinder the desired discrimination and comparison of different data sets. In particular the overlay of multiple raster layers is a problem, as overlapping images will not be transparent.
4. Supporting information on the map and information layers is weak. Some features that were asked for included an overview map showing the location of satellite/aircraft images and in situ data, and improved handling of colours and consistent colour coding for the same product by all providers.
5. Lack of near-real-time (NRT) access to some important observation data degrades the usefulness of the system for real emergency management. However, problems with NRT supply of certain types of data may occur in any monitoring system, and are not necessarily caused by the system itself.

The main recommendations for further development of DISPRO arising from the demonstrations are closely related to the shortcomings identified:

1. Improve the menu system for viewing and selecting layers to display. To get a more efficient and intuitive menu navigation, adopting a standardised grouping and layer naming scheme would help, as would implementing metadata in the "Notes" area more consistently. Drop-down menus could also be a means to ease the navigation and selection of layers.
2. Implement ways to better the identification and description of displayed layers. One suggestion was to let the currently displayed layers remain visible also when the group is closed. Showing the colour coding and symbols used in a separate area of the screen, would also be useful.
3. A better functionality for displaying time series of layers is needed. This is particularly important for model forecasts, where a time-stepping facility would have been very useful.
4. Improve the updating of available layers, allowing the layer menu to be updated in a more robust and predictable manner. The update frequency could be increased, i.e. configure DISPRO to less than 15 minutes between polling each data provider's DISPRO node, and providing informative messages if a node becomes unreachable during the update process.
5. Broaden the base of data providers, by incorporating providers outside the DISMAR consortium.
6. An online help would be useful. This could, among others, include a description of the grouping schema used, how layers are named, information about average delivery times for specific types of data and a news flash when error situations occur, causing problems with NRT acquisition.
7. Add the capability to inform about defined features on the map, enabling the user to click on e.g. a oil spill polygon to obtain additional information.

Implementing these enhancements was outside the scope of the current project, but illustrates the end-users' interest to incorporate DISPRO in their workflow, and a desire to maintain the system as a running service. In fact the realisation of the given recommendations would bring DISPRO close to being an operational GMES service, offering NRT access to satellite, aircraft and in situ observations, as well as derived parameters and model predictions. The timely provision of relevant data for pollution monitoring and risk assessment accessible through a common web browser, together with the ability to customise the user interface to individual needs and preferences, make DISPRO an attractive choice for users in public administrations and emergency services. With enhancements of functionality and establishment of streamlined processing chains and supporting infrastructure required in an operational context, DISPRO has the potential of becoming an integral part of a sustainable GMES service for pollution monitoring and forecasting in European ocean and coastal zone areas.

7 Multi-sensor data fusion techniques

Development and application of sensor fusion techniques in DISMAR project allows to retrieve and integrate data from disparate sources, including satellite and aircraft remote sensing data. Combination of data from multiple sources can significantly improve the accuracy of derived and predicted parameters, obtain and present necessary information in appropriate format, or even obtain qualitatively new information not available from single sensors. In marine pollution monitoring, the purpose of single- and multi-sensor systems is to provide the end-user with application-specific information. However, the acquisition of raw data alone may not entirely satisfy the needs of the end-user because the data may not contain the requested information, are inaccurate or parts of the data are corrupted by noise or simply missing. Application of sensor fusion techniques usually not only improve the quality of the raw data and associated with them low-level information but can help in derivation of high-level information and preparation of the final product for the end user.

Since different terminologies have been established for sensor data fusion, with some terms having different meaning, at the beginning of the project it was necessary to establish and clarify the common terms of reference and definitions used in data fusion. By definition of sensor fusion given by [W99], "data fusion is a formal framework in which are expressed means and tools for the alliance of data originating from different sources. It aims at obtaining information of greater quality; the exact definition of 'greater quality' will depend upon the application". In this definition, the "quality" is a generic term denoting that the resulting information is more satisfactory for the "customer" when performing the fusion process than that available from single informational sources.

In oil spill response, the information required by the end user include:

- detection of oil spill
- estimation of its spatial properties like extent and centre of mass
- a map visualizing the spatial distribution of oil thickness
- an estimate of the volume of the spilled oil
- an estimate of the oil class

The two main parameters are spatial coordinates of the detected oil spill and its thickness distribution. After detection of the oil spill and assessment of oil thickness, its spatial properties and approximate volume can be easier estimated. Thus, the project has mainly focused on the improved detection of oil spills using satellite data and on the estimation of the oil film thickness and evaluation of its spatial properties using airborne remotely sensed data. A third data fusion algorithm has been used to improve the spatial and spectral resolution of a merged MERIS-ETM product, which is used in algae monitoring. These algorithms are described in the following sections.

7.1 Airborne oil spill remote sensing: automated analysis and fusion of pollution data

The primary purpose of the airborne surveillance system described below is to avert dangers to the environment resulting from shipping in the North Sea and the Baltic Sea and from off-shore installations located in the North Sea [FMT98]. The aircraft sensor system installed onboard German maritime surveillance aircraft of Dornier 228-212 LM type includes a side-looking airborne radar (SLAR), an infrared/ultraviolet line scanner (IR/UV-LS), the Imaging Airborne Laser Fluorosensor (IALFS), and a scanning three-frequency microwave radiometer (MWR). These instruments allow measurements of oil spill parameters in different ranges of electromagnetic spectrum using active and passive technology. Due to differences in physical mechanisms underling their performance, the instruments are sensitive in different ranges of oil film thicknesses (except SLAR): for example, the minimum detectable oil film thickness of the NUV and TIR sensors lies in the sub-micron and the micron range, respectively. The sensor fusion algorithms developed in part during DISMAR project allow estimation oil spill optical thickness in a wider range of thicknesses, within a widest among all near range sensors swath width, and it in physical units.

The algorithms for analysis and fusion of aircraft data developed during the DISMAR project allow a spatial analysis of oil spills, the discrimination of ships and hot spots (due to thick oil), as well as the measurement and visualization of oil spill optical thickness within the field of view covered by those near-range sensors having the widest swath width. The Oil Spill Scene Analysis System (OSSAS),

presented in [R04], [R05] and [RHZ+05] is the fully-automated system consisted of two modules for 1) for generation of the real time, operator requested high-level information onboard the surveillance aircraft and 2) for generation of the additional, near-real time oil spill information in the data processing centre. The functional diagram of the system is presented in Figure 7-1.

Figure 7-1 Overall functional diagram of the oil spill scene analysis system (OSSAS).

The processing chain of OSSAS for the robust extraction of oil spill features from IR/UV-LS data (TIR and NUV images) consists of four steps:

1. Image enhancement,
2. Segmentation of the enhanced images is performed using the extended 2 D locally excitatory globally inhibitory oscillator network (LEGION) algorithm [C00], motivated by neurophysical concepts [TW95],
3. Oil spill segments analysis and computing the area, the centre of area, the tilt and the length/width ratio of each segment,
4. Sensor fusion to derive thickness estimates.

The fusion of the TIR and NUV segment maps allows the detection of thermal hot spots (due to thick oil) and the automated discrimination between thermal hot spots and ships. On the basis of modelled and reported detection limits [R05] the extracted thermal and ultraviolet features are used for the calculation of a minimum volume estimate. This estimate is part of a decision scheme for volume estimation based on IR/UV-LS, MWR, IALFS and fused NUV/IALFS information.

The fusion of NUV and IALFS data allows the estimation of a non-linear function relating absolutely calibrated IALFS data over the oil spill with NUV data, which are of higher spatial resolution than IALFS data, but which are only relatively calibrated. It was shown on the basis of field data that NUV images can be calibrated with IALFS data to give the *lidar optical thickness* $\kappa_{o,l}$ of the oil spill [R04], [R05]. So far, information on lidar optical thickness^{***} has only been available within the field of view (FOV) of the IALFS, i.e. FOV=28.4°. The proposed calibration procedure extends the measurement and visualization of lidar optical thickness to the FOV of the IR/UV-LS, i.e. FOV=87.3°. This is not only beneficial for visualisation, but also for enhanced volume estimation.

The result of the fused NUV/IALFS images of lidar optical thickness overlaid with extracted thermal and ultraviolet features is shown in Figure 7-2(a). This is the thickness map generated by OSSAS; all essential information required by the airborne sensor operator is integrated in a single map. As mentioned above, fused NUV/IALFS information on lidar optical thickness is included in a decision scheme for volume estimation. The high-level information products derived onboard the surveillance aircraft are not only useful for the airborne sensor operator. They are also beneficial for decision and response mechanisms on shore and at sea. Distribution of remote sensing data and data fusion products using internet-based GIS: The DISPRO system. Figure 7-2(b) shows an orthorectified SLAR image displayed on the Web Map Server interface of DISPRO. The SLAR image was acquired by the German maritime surveillance aircraft, serial number 57+01, over the Meldorf Bight area, Northern

^{***} The lidar optical thickness $\kappa_{o,l}$ is directly proportional to the thickness of the oil film. The IALFS-based measurement of $\kappa_{o,l}$ corresponds to an excitation wavelength of 308nm and a detection wavelength of 344nm (center wavelength of the water Raman band).

German Wadden Sea. The DISPRO system is capable of integrating any type of geo-referenced information. Examples are remote sensing data (satellite, aircraft, etc.), in situ data (e.g. autonomous moored and drifting platforms; [HCR+05]) model simulations (oil drift, phytoplankton blooms, etc.) and associated information products as derived using data fusion methods.

Figure 7-2 Fused NUV/IALFS image of lidar optical thickness (a) and Web Map Server interface of the DISPRO system showing an orthorectified SLAR image (b).

7.2 Satellite ENVISAT ASAR oil spill detection

Satellite synthetic aperture radars (SARs) due to their wide coverage, independence on natural light and weather conditions are found useful for the detection of oil spills [W96] and estimation of their parameters such as position and extent. The discrimination of oil spills is however in many cases ambiguous because other ocean phenomena can produce similar radar signatures to that of oil spills. These, e.g., can be low wind speed areas, organic films, grease ice, current shear zones, internal waves and others [EJJD+98] often jointly called "look-alikes". Computational approaches to oil spill detection based on Bayesian statistical theory [SSSV99] [FGN+00], neural network models [DPLC00] [ZBN97], and machine learning methods [KHM99] have proved to be effective (classification accuracies are in the range 76-94% for oil spills and 86-99% for look-alikes); operational classification is still based on expert visual analysis of SAR data or on semi-automatic procedures for oil spill detection. There are several reasons for this including: 1) deficiencies in SAR image segmentation especially in low-wind conditions, 2) necessity to use additional information for classification (e.g. high spatial resolution local wind fields, probability of natural organic films) which is not always available, 3) relatively low or not well known generalisation of the developed algorithms due to high natural variability of the spill parameters.

The prototype of the oil spill detection system for the detection of oil slicks in ENVISAT ASAR images has been developed during DISMAR project. The detection system uses segment-based approach for detection of oil spills. It incorporates modules for image import, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification. The task of improved detection of oil spill has been addressed 1) by analysis of image features-segments attributes, and proposal of new features describing multi-polarisation image content, and 2) due to increased number of input features with unknown distribution, the special attention has been paid to the development and training of the classification algorithm. A new sensor fusion algorithm for the detection of oil spills based on Support Vector Machine (SVM) [CS00] has been developed and its performance has been compared with performance of multi-layer feed-forward neural network model (MLP) [R58] trained by error back-propagation algorithm.

Figure 7-3 Examples of segmented ENVISAT ASAR image fragments containing oil spills (26 June, 2003) detected by the algorithm.

SVMs are learning systems that use kernel functions to map original input space to higher dimensional kernel feature space where the data can be linearly separated. The learning algorithm of SVM originating from optimisation theory uses the concept of margins and accounts for factors, defined by Vapnik and Chervonenkis (VC) theory, in order to guarantee its good generalisation. It is very powerful method that in the few years since its introduction has already outperformed most other systems in a wide variety of applications [CS00]. The two classifiers (SVM and MLP) have been trained using cases of oil spills and look-alikes selected from 10 ENVISAT ASAR images acquired at APP mode; and parameters of the SVM have been optimised using "grid search" algorithm. Application of SVM with image features described below allows correct classification of 100% and 89% of the test oil spills and look-alikes cases, respectively. Using limited training data set SVM algorithm provides more stable classification results than neural network based classifier. Examples of detected oil spills are presented in Figure 7-3.

For the successive discrimination of oil films from look-alikes it is important to find image features containing sufficient information on separation of these ocean phenomena. The usual set of image features used for the detection of oil spills in SAR images includes power to mean ratio, energy contrast, spill complexity, moment invariants, and some other features (see ref. above). Polarisation information contained in fully polarimetric data set has been found promising [F03] [MTC05] for the discrimination of oil films from look-alikes, while polarisation ratio, traditionally used in cases where phase information is unavailable, provides poor discrimination capability. ENVISAR ASAR operating in APP mode can acquire images at two different polarisations, thus providing an interesting opportunity to explore multipolarisation information. A new set of features describing association between two polarisations (VV and HH polarizations) including entropy based features: conditional entropy, uncertainty coefficients, joint uncertainty and the ratio of eigenvalues characterising the form of distribution have been proposed in DISMAR project for the improved detection of oil spills. Using the available training and test data sets, the preliminary results, which need to be verified in future, show that total the total accuracy improvement is about 5.5-8.5 % changing from 83,5% for single polarisation data (VV) with standard image features to 89-92 % when different sets of multi-polarisation features are additionally used.

7.3 Fusion of ENVISAT MERIS and Landsat TM data

Ocean colour monitoring is usually based on optical remote sensing with spatial resolutions of approx. 1 km. This spatial scale is available from sensors like AVHRR and SeaWiFS, which have a swath width of approx. 2500 and 2800 kilometres, respectively, and allow daily or more frequent revisits in most areas. The ENVISAT MERIS sensor has a spatial resolution of 300 meters, 15 spectral bands and a 3-day revisit period. Even if this resolution is finer than for most oceanographic sensors, it is too coarse for monitoring coastal waters, where physical and biological phenomena require a finer spatial resolution [M99]. Multispectral Landsat ETM (Enhanced Thematic Mapper) images have a spatial resolution of approx. 30 meters, but only 4 spectral bands. A method for fusing these two data sources, to improve the spatial and spectral resolutions of the merged product has been proposed in [ZOLR99], and tested on simulated MERIS images in [MMPP01]. The resulting image has a 30 m spatial resolution (ETM spatial resolution) and 15 spectral bands (MERIS spectral resolution).

This study has tested the data fusion algorithm on real MERIS data. Figure 7-4(a) shows a colour composite of the input ETM image (1000x1000 pixels) and Figure 7-4(b) the input MERIS Level 1b image (100x100 pixels) in radiance. A zoom factor of 10 has been applied to this image in order to emphasise the difference between the ETM and MERIS resolutions. Figure 7-4(c) shows the resulting image, which is characterized by 15 spectral bands and a 30 m resolution. By comparing figures Figure 7-4(b) and Figure 7-4(c), a spatial improvement can be seen

The overall MERIS image radiometry is well preserved as the ETM image geometry. The post-fusion visibility of the boundaries between classes is noticeable especially on areas with reduced radiometric dynamics, e.g. over the stretch of sea water.

Figure 7-5(a) shows a colour composite of the input ETM image (1000 x 1000 pixels) and Figure 7-5(b) shows the input MERIS Level 2 image (100 x 100 pixels) in reflectance. MERIS level 2 images involve a new problem for the fusion due to some "black pixels" located on land-water borders. Due to atmospheric correction methods being different on land and water, these mixed pixels have not been corrected by one of the atmospheric corrections and their radiometry in MERIS level 2 images is zero. The 3rd step of the fusion process cannot then be achieved and these pixels have to then be ignored.

The overall MERIS image reflectance is still as well preserved as the ETM image geometry. However, the post-fusion visibility of the boundaries between classes is noticeable. The output image has the spatial characteristics of ETM and the spectral and radiometric characteristics of MERIS (image in reflectance).

The robustness of the fusion is measured by means of the ERGAS parameter [RAA+03], which is derived from RSME estimation as follows:

$$ERGAS(X, Y) = 100 * \frac{h}{l} \sqrt{\frac{1}{nb} \sum_{\lambda=1}^{nb} \frac{[RMSE(X, Y, \lambda)]^2}{[mean(X - Y, \lambda)]^2}}$$

where X is the original MERIS image, Y the resulting image of fusion, h the ETM resolution (30m), l the MERIS resolution (300m), λ the spectral band, and nb the total number of spectral bands.

An increase in ERGAS was found, and can be explained by two reasons. First, the classification applied to the ETM image smoothes the radiometric variability. Secondly, the delay between the two image acquisitions, in which landscape change may have taken place.

This study has shown that a MERIS and an ETM image can be fused to obtain a merged product with the best characteristics of each sensor: the high spectral resolution of MERIS and the high spatial resolution of ETM. Use of the ERGAS parameter allowed testing of the sensitivity to changes in landscape between the two image acquisitions. Further discussion of validation can be found in [MMP+05].

Figure 7-4 An ETM image (a), a MERIS Level 1b image (b) and the fused image (c).

Figure 7-5 An ETM image (a), a MERIS Level 2 image (b), and the fused image (c).

8 Dissemination

Dissemination has focused on users representing public administrations and emergency services including national environmental authorities in charge of crisis management in the case of marine pollution events. Project results have been disseminated through presentations, posters and brochures at conferences and workshops, the project web site (<http://www.nersc.no/Project/dismar/>), as well as in journals and conference proceedings.

DISMAR results has been presented at a number of conferences, workshops and user meetings, including among others:

- IGARSS'03, Toulouse, July 2003
- COASTGIS'03, Genova, October 2003
- GMES Meeting, Baveno, November 2003
- ECO-IMAGINE, Seville, May 2004
- OCEANIDES Workshop, Copenhagen, May 2004
- ENVISAT & ERS Symposium, Salzburg, September 2004
- IC EST 2005, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, January 2005
- New Space Services for Maritime Users: The Impact of Satellite Technology on Maritime Legislation, Paris, February 2005
- 2nd EARSeL Workshop Coastal Zone, Porto, June 2005
- EuroGOOS 2005, Brest, June 2005
- 31st International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment, St. Petersburg, June 2005
- MERIS-AATSR User Workshop, Frascati, September 2005

Appendix A contains a list of presentations, posters and papers made during the project. Other publications include articles in e.g. the OGC newsletter (March 2004) and the GIS Ireland newsletter (June 2004). Fact sheets (brochures) were prepared for each of the demo regions, and for the DISPRO system. These were handed out at many of the events listed above and made available through the DISPRO portal (<http://dispro.ucc.ie/apps/dismar/>). Results have also been presented in 3 journal papers, and one book chapter has been produced with input from the project. The referee publications are also listed in Appendix A. In addition, workshops and telephone conferences have been held for users in each demonstration area (Table 8-1).

Table 8-1 User workshops organised in DISMAR.

Demo area	Date	User organisations attending
North Sea/Skagerrak	18 March 2005	SFT (State Pollution Agency)
North Sea/Skagerrak	11 October 2005	SFT (State Pollution Agency)
North Sea/Skagerrak	28 October 2005	Norwegian Fisheries Authorities
Coast of Germany	25 January 2005	Central Command for Maritime Emergencies Germany (CCME)
Coast of Germany	20 September 2005	Central Command for Maritime Emergencies Germany (CCME)
Coast of France	28 September 2004	CEDRE Emergency Team
Coast of France	3 February 2005	CEDRE Emergency Team and Ifremer personnel
Coast of France	12 October 2005	CEDRE Emergency Team
Coast of France	3 November 2005	MRCC-La Garde/Mediterranean
Coast of Italy	13 July 2004	Laboratorio di Biologia Marina – Provincia di Bari, ARPAB (Basilicata Regional Agency for the Environment)
Coast of Italy	14 September 2005	Laboratorio di Biologia Marina – Provincia di Bari, ARPAB (Basilicata Regional Agency for the Environment)
W. English Channel	10 August 2004	Fisheries Research Services, Marine Lab. Aberdeen
W. English Channel	20-21 October 2005	Fisheries Research Service, Marine Lab. Aberdeen, Satellite Observing Systems
All regions	25 May 2004	OCEANIDES Workshop on Oil Spill Monitoring, incl. Among other EEA and JRC personnel
All regions	24 November 2004	Second Meeting of EGEMP (European Group of Experts on satellite Monitoring and assessment of sea-based oil Pollution)
All regions	20 April 2005	Third Meeting of EGEMP (European Group of Experts on satellite Monitoring and assessment of sea-based oil Pollution)

9 Assessment and evaluation

In DISMAR, an Advisory Group assessed the results at key milestones during the project, based on the review of deliverables and testing of the developed DISPRO prototype. The Advisory Group consisted of:

- Mr. Lasse H. Pettersson, Leading Scientist, NERSC
- Dr. Nicholas Holden, Science Manager, Environmental Agency, UK
- Dr. Joe Silke, Section Manager (acting), Marine Institute, Galway, Ireland
- Mr. Robin Berglund, Senior Research Scientist, Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT)
- Dr. Carsten Brockmann, Brockmann Consult, Germany

The assessment were carried out with respect to the predefined success criteria for the project:

S1: To what extent is the **system design and architecture** and advancement compared to similar systems, and how well does it satisfy requirements for decision support system for risk assessment and crisis management? (Milestone M1, month 6)

S2: To what extent is the proposed **structure of data and products (including metadata)** capable of handling all relevant data, and how are data formats compatible with existing standards? (Milestone M2, month 12)

S3: Is the **development of DISPRO-1 prototype** in agreement with the system design and architecture described in D2, and is the implementation following the planned schedule? (Milestone M3, month 22)

S4: To what extent are **data and model products** developed in the project important for the decision support system for risk assessment and crisis management? (Milestone M2 and M3, month 12 and 22)

S5: To what extent has the **demonstration of DISPRO-1** shown that the first prototype can deliver information for a decision support system? (Milestone M4, month 24)

S6: How useful can the investigated **data fusion methods** be as part of the decision support system? (Milestone M4, month 24)

S7: Is the **development of DISPRO-2 prototype** in agreement with the system design and architecture and the evaluation after month 24? (Milestone M5, month 34)

S8: To what extent has the **demonstration of DISPRO-2** shown that the second prototype can deliver information for a decision support system? (Milestone M6, month 36)

Success criteria S1: System design and architecture

Criteria S1 was assessed based on deliverable D2 (Report on requirement analysis and prototype design), which concluded with:

The DISPRO design and architecture suggested is an advancement through the approach of introducing a multi-tiered distributed web structure and OpenGIS architecture for data exchange, use and analysis. Due to lack of end-user contact, the report is weak in the issues related to crisis management and assessment taking advantage of the existing infrastructure and practice for handling such events. The following comments should be taken into account in the further project implementation: Select "one" end-user for each application area in each country and identify their current mode of operations, contingency plans, information/data sources and their utilization. Identify the clear benefit/role of DISPRO to these users. Use this experience to tailor a "generic" DISPRO system including the actual, external and internal to DISMAR consortium, data and information sources to be included.

User involvement was improved during the development of DISPRO-1 and DISPRO-2, and the feedback obtained was used to enhance and extend the prototype. In hindsight, however, we see that a stronger involvement of more users, for instance as project partners like CEDRE, could have further improved the developed prototype.

Success criteria S2: Structure of data and products

S2 was assessed based on a review of deliverable D5.1 (Report on data harmonisation and metadata). The review concluded that:

The report meets the specifications given in the description of work and provides justified and clear recommendations with respect to data and metadata organisation. However, the document would be more complete if a concrete list of metadata was included. In the further project work main efforts should be on how the project can commonly agree and meet these specifications in its actual data provision to DISPRO. The issues raised are possible for inclusion in the 2nd edition of this report due later in the project.

The development of a metadata schema for DISPRO was undertaken and the resulting XML encoding with examples can be found in deliverable D5.2 [HOTu05]. The DISPRO metadata schema was developed as a profile of ISO 19115, and its contents was duly discussed and agreed among the partners to ensure all needed metadata elements were incorporated.

Success criteria S3: DISPRO-1 development in line with design

S3 was evaluated based on review of deliverables D6.1 (Progress report on DISPRO-1 development), D6.2 (Final report on DISPRO-1) and testing of DISPRO-1. The main conclusions of the assessment was as follows:

DISPRO-1 has demonstrated distribution of the proposed types of data, although in most regions there are only a few base layers available. This is however not a limitation of the system, which does not discriminate between base and other data layers. The three main types of observed and forecasted data, i.e. remote sensing, in situ and model data, have all been ample demonstrated through numerous examples provided by several nodes. The overall design of DISPRO-1 has been realised, with the subsystems named in D6.1 and D6.2 (portal, web GIS client, WMS client, WMS server, geo-processing service, local web server, aggregator, XML native database and metadata catalogue). However, the amount of background material on oil spill and algal blooms should be increased, and the ability to have a more dynamic document viewer, preferably in a web-based form, should be explored in DISPRO-2. Also, the inclusion of a geo-processing service should be attempted in DISPRO-2 to show that chosen technology can facilitate such services in a Web GIS system. A candidate service, met.no's OD3D oil drift model, has been identified, and is planned to be included.

The feedback from the demonstrations of DISPRO-1 was synthesised into a list of requirements for enhancements and additional functionality that were desired in DISPRO-2. After prioritisation and review of available resources, most of the requirements were implemented in the final version of the prototype. For instance, the candidate service for oil spill drift prediction was implemented as a stand-alone service (Figure 3-25), but the results could be made available through DISPRO-2. Some requirements, like a dedicated document viewer, however, could not be realised within the frames of the projects.

Success criteria S4: Data and model products

Criteria S4 was assessed based on a review of deliverables D3.2 (Second report on data products and models), D4.1 (First report on new data products), and D7.1 (First demonstration and validation of DISPRO-1). These reports included products from satellite remote sensing data (ASAR, MERIS, MODIS, AVHRR, SeaWiFS), aircraft data (IR/UV, lasers, microwave instruments), in situ sensors (X-band radar, Ferrybox systems), oil drift forecasting models (OD3D, the Adriatic Sea oil drift model), and ecological model (POLCOMS-ERSEM).

The overall conclusion was positive:

The listed data sources for remote sensing data are the most relevant available today, while the list of in situ data sources should be extended with other available sources, e.g. measurements from fixed locations (such as buoys or water samples regularly made at the same position). The models used in the project are well described in the reports, are fit for purpose, scientifically sound and accepted in the marine community. The metadata used in DISPRO-1 enable searching for available data, but should be considered extended with technical metadata in the second version of DISPRO. With the exception of few in situ data sets available, the products demonstrated in DISPRO-1 are well suited for decision-support in operational oil spill and algae bloom monitoring and forecasting. The DISMAR partners are advised to look into other existing monitoring systems and how these integrate observations in their processing and analysis chain.

The DISPRO metadata schema allows for entering a link to a full technical metadata resource. Hence, the data providers could provide additional metadata for their products, even if the project did not have resources needed to develop or adopt a profile of this type of metadata.

Success criteria S5: Demonstration of DISPRO-1 successful

Criteria S5 was assessed based on reviewing deliverable D7.1 (First demonstration and validation of DISPRO-1) and testing the DISPRO-1 prototype. The overall conclusions were as follows:

DISPRO-1 has clearly demonstrated the proof-of-concept of the chosen OGC and W3C technologies, both in terms of setting up the different subsystems and in preparing data layers and associated metadata according to the principles laid out in the design phase. DISPRO's ability to provide instant access to a number of data providers through a common entry point, and enabling easy configuration of which providers deliver data to a specific region and automatic generation of the Web GIS Client based on the layers available upon login, are seen as the main strengths of the system. Several suggestions for improvements in the last year of the project given, most importantly to increase the functionality of the client and to develop these new features in close cooperation with end-users, who can give rapid feedback both on DISPRO-2 and the new products that will be made available. It was also recommended to assess the amount of work needed on the data providers' side to set up a node with layers and associated metadata, as well as to consider if the metadata schema used should be extended for the last demonstration.

The list of desired enhancements and new features was analysed and prioritised to maximise user benefits versus the cost of implementation. The final version of the prototype, DISPRO-2, included most of these requirements and was favourably evaluated, cf. section 6.8 and deliverable D7.2 [HH05b]. Section 4 and deliverable D5.2 [HOTu05] describes the main steps needed for an organisation wanting to deliver data through DISPRO.

Success criteria S6: Data fusion method applicable

The Advisory Group evaluated criteria S6 based on a review of deliverable D8.1 (First Report on Multi-Source Data Fusion: Part 1: State-of-the-art. Review and Terms of Reference. Part 2: Algorithms and processed data.). This review concluded that:

A common terminology for data fusion has been established and state-of-the-art algorithms reviewed. A first implementation of some algorithms has been carried out and tested on a single data source simulating multi-source data by deriving multiple texture measures from the SAR. In the last year, it is crucial to test the developed algorithms on (real) multi-source data. Also, the usefulness of the data fusion methods should be asked directly from the users, to tune individual algorithms and select the most appropriate one for the different regions and application areas (oil spill/algae bloom).

During the last year of the project, data fusion algorithms were tested and evaluated using different types of remote sensing EO data from the DISMAR Category-1 project and national projects, and multi-sensor remote sensing data from the German maritime surveillance aircrafts. The fused data products were included in the demonstrations and evaluated together with the other single-source data products. User feedback was used to improve the algorithms, and recommendations made for selection between different types of algorithms based on their classification accuracies (section 7).

Success criteria S7: Development of DISPRO-2 in line with system design and architecture

The Advisory Group assessed criteria S7 by reviewing deliverable D6.3 (Final report on DISPRO-2) and testing of DISPRO-2. The main points of the assessment were:

DISPRO-2 is in agreement with the system design and architecture defined earlier in the project, and follows the recommendations from the Advisory Group's evaluation after month 24. Work has been done to get used feedback in a systematic way for all target user groups. The feedback is largely positive, with many comments about how to improve the system, which motivates further work using this architecture. Generally, the DISPRO-2 encompasses most of the improvements suggested for DISPRO-1. Clearly, several aspects of the user interface and pre-defined profiles for information retrieval can be further improved. Also, some of the evaluation data sets are only available for demonstration periods and not regularly delivered. However, the DISPRO-2 system contains a large potential for becoming an operational GMES service. Thus, it is strongly encouraged that these developments take place in order to take full advantage of the capabilities of such as system. Tailored applications with a few "homogenous" user categories might the constellation to do this development.

The system design and architecture defined in the beginning of the project have proven to be flexible and extensible. Thus, DISPRO-2 could be built in agreement with the initial recommendations, even if a number of new and improved features were incorporated, and substantial changes in the underlying technologies and tools occurred during the project period. The partners agree that DISPRO-2 has the potential of becoming an integral part of a sustainable GMES service for pollution monitoring and forecasting in European ocean and coastal zone areas, given that the recommendations from the final demonstration and evaluation are taken into account.

Success criteria S8: Demonstration of DISPRO-2 successful

Criteria S8 was assessed based on reviewing deliverable D7.2 (Second demonstration and validation of DISPRO-2) and testing the DISPRO-2 prototype. The overall conclusions were as follows:

Generally, the DISPRO-2 demonstration shows that the users easily can access and navigate between the information sources available. As commented by several users, the organisation of the interactive menus and lists of data sources could have been made more intuitive. Nevertheless, even a novice user could after a short time of testing and familiarising with the system, easily access the data sources needed. Some complexity is introduced by the non-existence (use) of a consistent terminology for the data available from different providers. This lack of consistent terminology may possibly be due to limited availability of users within the project consortium.

DISPRO shows nicely the capabilities of WMS technology to combine map layers in the same client from different map servers hosted by different service providers and how this combination is implemented in practice. The demonstrations illustrate the capabilities and some of the technical problems that have to be overcome before using this as an operational tool. Despite the more generic nature of DISPRO-2, the system is capable of meeting the information needs of the various user groups as well as various nations. The capabilities of handling time series with rapid updates of data could have been improved.

The DISMAR Advisory Group agrees with the users' responses from the demonstrations of DISPRO-2, and sites the conclusions of [HH05b] on:

"The overall user response to DISPRO-2 has been very positive, and the primary strengths of the system can be summarised as follows: The system

- provides a simple and easy to use interface, having an intuitive layout
- demonstrates the ability to integrate diverse data and information from distributed sources
- offers an impressive mix of information content in the different demonstration areas
- is well suited for assessing emergency management in retrospect, i.e. for past incidents
- demonstrates near-real-time data acquisition of dedicated products for pollution monitoring

A further advantage was that all data and information could be accessed through a common web browser, with no need for plug-ins. On the other hand, the second demonstration phase also identified some remaining shortcomings and led to recommendations for future enhancements:

- improving the menu system for viewing and selecting layers to display
- implementing a better and consistent way of identifying and describing displayed layers
- facilitate better handling of time series of layers, e.g. through time-stepping and/or animations
- improving the updating of available layers
- increasing the amount of data and information, by including providers outside the DISMAR project
- providing online help, describing available functionality and how to use it
- adding a query function providing information on displayed features, e.g. oil spill polygons"

The full exploitation and improvement of DISPRO-2 for a dedicated application area – regionally or Europe-wide – is strongly recommended. Such development will probably remove some of the deficiencies identified and more clearly demonstrate the full potential existing in the system.

The providers in the consortium also have overall positive experiences with the development and demonstration of DISPRO-2, and therefore plan to build on the results for future GMES services. Many important issues were raised by the users involved in the demonstrations, as well as by the Advisory Group, including the points made above. To develop an operational GMES service, issues such as enhanced functionality, more base layers and ancillary material, establishment of fully streamlined processing chains and supporting infrastructures, must be addressed and solved. Tailoring DISPRO-2 to a specific application area should be done in close co-operation with stakeholders to ensure that the resulting system satisfies their needs in an operational context.

10 Conclusions and recommendations

The DISMAR project has focused on three main areas of research and technological development for marine pollution monitoring and forecasting within the context of GMES: (1) product, algorithm and model development, (2) DISPRO design and implementation, including metadata and data harmonisation, and (3) demonstration to end-users in targeted European ocean and coastal zone regions. The main achievements of each main area are summarised below.

Product, algorithm and model development

A number of algorithms and models for generation of products useful for marine pollution monitoring and forecasting have been developed and tested during the project.

Algorithms for satellite radar data have been extended to handle new ENVISAT ASAR data, and verified against cases of known oil spills in different ocean and coastal zone regions. Both automatic and operator-controlled algorithms have been evaluated. While automatic algorithms can quickly identify potential spill candidates, they often report false positives as spills, and a trained operator should examine the output of such algorithms, correlating it with other available data, e.g. meteorological, sea state and known locations of offshore installations and ship routes, to obtain more reliable results.

Ocean colour data are now available from a number of different sensors. New algorithms and near-real-time processing chains for ENVISAT MERIS and Aqua/Terra-MODIS data have been developed and set up during the project. In addition, a comparison study between the different sensors have been carried out, concluding that while the ocean colour products from MERIS, Aqua-MODIS and SeaWiFS, were in fair agreement, the algorithms used for processing of Terra-MODIS data should be reviewed in detail and improved.

The validation of an ecological model simulation of the western English Channel highlighted varying model performance for different variables. Results are consistently good for temperature but suggest that further improvements must be made in the model ability to simulate phytoplankton before the POLCOMS-ERSEM system can be used to confidently forecast ecological variables.

The German maritime surveillance aircrafts are equipped with multiple sensors, including IR/UV (infrared/ultraviolet), lasers and microwave instruments. In DISMAR, an algorithmic framework for automated analysis and fusion of IR/UV and imaging laser fluorosensor data has been developed and tested. The resulting fused oil spill thickness product has a higher spatial resolution and larger swath width than that which can be obtained from the imaging laser fluorosensor (IALFS) sensor alone. A new data fusion algorithm for multi-polarisation ASAR data, based on Support Vector Machine classifier and neural network models, has also been developed. The algorithm has been tested on a small test data set, where the total classification accuracy was clearly improved compared to using only a single channel ASAR image.

Ship- or land-based X-band radar is a new data source for detection of slicks on the sea surface, and new algorithms for processing and analysis of these data have been developed. These data have been used in the German demonstrations, and the project has shown that X-band radar data can be used to detect accumulated surface material and allows separation of thick layers within a convergence area from thin layers within passively drifting slicks.

New above water radiance sensors have been tested as a part of a Ferrybox system mounted on a ferry using existing algorithms for extraction of chlorophyll-a and total suspended matter. The algorithms used were not tuned to the demo region, but still demonstrated the capability to provide independent measurements of ocean colour parameters for quality control of satellite data used in algal bloom monitoring.

DISPRO development including metadata and data harmonisation

DISPRO development started with a broad survey of user requirements for marine pollution monitoring and forecasting in the partner countries. We also reviewed the INSPIRE architecture and infrastructure documents to devise a flexible and robust design for DISPRO. These activities resulted in a recommendation to use the OGC WMS protocol as the basis for DISPRO, as the majority of data was raster data (the WMS also handles vector data). Several other standards were also used, including

JavaScript, CSS, Cocoon, and eXist. With the rapid rate of change and innovation in web-based GIS and services, understanding and integrating the latest version of technologies and tools was a constant challenge. The underlying modular design with standardisation of subsystem communication protocols, and the use of XML as the encoding mechanism for both service and metadata descriptions, however, alleviated some of the technical difficulties of DISPRO development.

Data and metadata harmonisation were needed to make the different data repositories in DISPRO interoperable, and existing standards for geographic metadata and data were reviewed and evaluated, to find a flexible and extensible solution to this problem. This work led to an initial recommendation to implement a metadata structure compliant with the Core Metadata element set of ISO 19115, and to encode it in XML. As no standard XML encoding was available during the project, the partners developed the DISPRO metadata schema using W3C XML Schema, to represent the chosen ISO 19115 profile. This metadata specification was tested in the first demonstration phase and proved to be robust and sufficient for the project. Hence, only minor changes were made for the second and final demonstration phase.

Demonstrations for end-users in European ocean and coastal zone regions

DISPRO was demonstrated in two phases, within five European ocean and coastal zone regions: (1) North Sea/Skagerrak, (2) Coast of Germany, (3) Coast of France, (4) Coast of Italy, and (5) Western English Channel. In the first demonstration, users generally appreciated the concept of DISPRO and found the provided layers useful, but in many cases requested additional layers and new or enhanced functionality. Based on user feedback, as well as comments from the project's Advisory Board and the IST Annual Review's Expert Panel, DISPRO was continually enhanced and extended for the final demonstration.

DISPRO-2 was also demonstrated in all five regions, with demonstrations aiming to show how the layers produced initially for each of the five regions can be integrated into a pan-European system. Many of the requests made in the first phase were now implemented, and duly acknowledged by users. However, some features were still perceived as missing or unsatisfactory by different users. Some of these requests are included under "Service facilities" below.

Recommendations for future GMES services

The DISMAR project allowed us to build competence and capacity, giving hands-on experience with state-of-the-art standards and tools for geo-spatial data and metadata as well as web-based GIS. We also got valuable feedback from the project's Advisory Group, the Expert Panel of the IST Annual Reviews and the end-users involved in the demonstrations. Based on these experiences and feedback, we recommend the following for development of future GMES services for marine environmental monitoring and forecasting:

Metadata:

- Discovery and technical metadata should be based on the ISO 19115 standard [ISO03b].
- ISO 19139 [ISO05] should be used as the encoding of ISO 19115 metadata, for both discovery and technical metadata.
- Discovery metadata for the products should also be provided using Dublin Core [DCMI03], to allow products to be accessible from a number of web-based search engines. (Ideally, a Dublin Core profile will be extractable from an ISO 19139 profile.) In addition, a XSLT stylesheet [W3C99] for transformation of Dublin Core encoded XML files into HTML should be prepared, for easy presentation to users.

Data:

- Vector data should be made available for downloading as Shapefiles or GML.
- Raster data should be made available for downloading as GeoTIFF, TIFF, JPEG or HDF files.
- Gridded data should be made available for downloading as NetCDF or HDF files. These binary standard formats are well suited for high volume data, like model forecasts and high-resolution satellite imagery.
- For delivery of data through a system like DISPRO, the above types of data can be used as well as a spatially enabled database, like e.g. PostgreSQL, ArcIMS or Oracle.

Portal and Client systems development:

- The development should be based on OGC, W3C and other web services standards, specifically WMS, WFS and WCS, XML, XSD, XSLT, JavaScript, CSS and (X)HTML.
- Users should be able to access all products and services through a common web browser, without having to install any additional plug-ins. No COTS software should be required on the users' side.

Service facilities:

- The service should be able to handle time series in an intuitive manner. For instance, it should be easy to step through a model forecast and a time series of satellite images.
- The menu organisation and indication of selected layers need improvement. There should be some way of showing which layers are currently selected (and displayed) even if the enclosing group is collapsed.
- The service should provide more information on the displayed layers, such as the legends and symbols used, and a consistent scheme for colours and symbols should be enforced for all regions.
- Enhanced display capabilities for images should be developing, including e.g. transparent overlay of multiple raster layers, and simple facilities for colour manipulation of raster data.
- The amount of available data should be increased by including more data providers. (This would not require any changes to DISPRO, just adding another "node" to the data supplier list, after the terms of data delivery and use have been agreed with the new data provider.)
- Access to data in near-real-time (NRT) should be improved. (For delivery of input data to a service, this is primarily an issue of improving the provider's infrastructure, and possibly involving data policies.)
- The service should offer downloading of products in one of the above standard formats. Some of the products may be available to specific users or user groups, and the service should handle the access rights' issues related to such products. Export of currently displayed data, e.g. for use in a report, should be included. This is available through a screenshot or right clicking on the map and choosing "save image as".
- More ancillary information should be provided, e.g. documents on regulation, emergency plans, etc. The system should standardise on PDF and HTML for this type of information, to make it easy to display (and print).
- An online help would be useful, providing e.g. information about data providers, restrictions and/or potential problems with NRT data delivery, product descriptions, etc.

As an overall guideline, future recommendations of INSPIRE and GMES initiatives should be taken into account. In service development, results from other EC and ESA funded GMES projects, should also be utilised provided they are based on open technologies and standards.

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12 Technical Terms and Abbreviations

Architecture	The models, standards, technologies, specifications, and procedures used to represent, transform and generally accommodate the integration, maintenance and use of information in digital format. [from INSPIRE]
ASAR	Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar
CDOM	Coloured, Dissolved Organic Matter
CGI	Common Gateway Interface, a standard for how external programs interface with HTTP servers
Component	A group of technically similar functionalities within the architecture. [from INSPIRE]
CSML	Climate Science Mark-Up Language
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DC	Dublin Core
ECMAScript	JavaScript standard produced by European Computer Manufacturers Association
EO	Earth Observation
FGDC	The United States Federal Geographic Data Committee
FLH	Fluorescence Line Height
FTU	Formazine Turbidity Unit
GIS	Geographic Information System
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security
GML	Geography Markup Language
HAB	Harmful Algal Bloom
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
HTTP	Hypertext transfer protocol, the network protocol as used by the World Wide Web.
INSPIRE	The INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe
MERIS	The MEedium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer Instrument
MODIS	The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SeaWiFS	The Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol
TSM	Total Suspended Matter
Web Services	Programmatic interfaces exposed for application to application communication via the web.
XHTML	HTML 4 reformulated as an XML application.
XML	eXtensible Markup language
XSD	XML Schema Definition
XSDL	XML Schema Definition Language
WMS	Web Map Service
XSLT	XSL (Extensible Stylesheet Language) Transformations

Appendices

Appendix A. DISMAR Deliverables and Selected Publications

DISMAR Deliverables:

Del.No	Deliverable name	Availability
D1	Project presentation	Public
D2	Requirements analysis and prototype design	Restricted
D9.1	Dissemination and use plan	Restricted
D3.1	First report on data products and models	Public
D5.1	First report on data harmonisation and metadata	Restricted
D6.1	Progress Report on DISPRO	Public
D1.1	Annual Report year 1	IST/Public*
D10.1	Assessment and evaluation after year 1	Restricted
D3.2	Second Report on Data Products and Models	Public
D4.1	First report on new data products	Public
D6.2	Final Report on DISPRO-1	Public
D8.1	First Report on Multi-Source Data Fusion. Part 1 - State-of-the-art. Review and Terms of Reference. Part 2 - Algorithms and processed data.	Restricted
D7.1	First demonstration and validation of DISPRO-1	IST
D9.2	First set of dissemination material (brochures)	Public
D1.2	Second Annual Report year 2	IST/Public*
D10.2	Assessment and evaluation after year 2	Restricted
D5.2	Final Report on data harmonisation and metadata	Public
D4.2	Final report on new data products	Public
D6.3	Final Report on DISPRO-2	Public
D8.2	Final report on multi-source data fusion and algorithms	Public
D7.2	Report from demonstration and validation of DISPRO-2 (Public
D9.3	Final set of dissemination material (brochures)	Public
D9.4	Technology Implementation Plan	Restricted
D11	DISMAR Final Report	Public

All public deliverables are available on the project's web site: <http://www.nerisc.no/Projects/dismar/>.

*The management part of the annual report is available to IST only; the scientific part is public.

Selected publications:

In referee journals:

- Nils Robbe and Oliver Zielinski: 'Airborne remote sensing of oil spills - analysis and fusion of multi-spectral near-range data'. Journal of Marine Science and Environment, Part C2.
- F. Nirchio (ASI), M. Sorgente (ASI), A. Giancaspro (TPZ), W. Biamino (UNIPO), E. Parisato (UNIPO), R. Ravera (UNIPO) and P. Trivero (UNIPO). "Automatic detection of oil spills from SAR images". International Journal of Remote Sensing, Vol. 26, No. 6, 20 March 2005, 11571174.
- Minghelli-Roman, Audrey, Mathieu-Marni, S., Polidori, L., Loubersac, L., Cauneau, F.: Spatial Resolution Improvement of real MeRIS Images By Fusion With Landsat/ETM Images. *To be published in IEEE Trans. On GeoScience and Remote Sensing (accepted)*.
- 'Detection of oil spills by airborne sensors' by O. Zielinski, T. Hengstermann and N. Robbe in the book 'Marine Surface Films: Chemical Characteristics, Influence on Air-Sea Interactions, and Remote Sensing' edited by M. Gade, H. Hühnerfuss and G. Korenowski. To be published by Springer.

In proceedings of conferences and workshops, online journals, reports, white papers, etc.:

- Éamonn Ó Tuama (CMRC), Clive Best (JRC) and Torill Hamre (NERSC), "A Web-based Distributed Architecture for Coastal Zone Management", in CoastGIS'03 Conference Proceedings. Online: http://www.gisig.it/coastgis/papers/o_tuama.htm
- Cysewski M.; „Radar Scanning for Hydrography“; GKSS report 2003/26, October 2003
- Éamonn Ó Tuama (CMRC), Clive Best (JRC) and Torill Hamre (NERSC), "DISPRO: A WEB-BASED DISTRIBUTED ARCHITECTURE FOR COASTAL ZONE MANAGEMENT". DISMAR article in OGC newsletter article (http://www.opengis.org/press/?page=ogcuser&view=20040324_ogcuser)

- Éamonn Ó Tuama (CMRC), “DISMAR – implementing an OpenGIS compliant Marine Information Management System”. Published in GIS Ireland, the newsletter of the Irish organisation for geographic information.
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- Oliver Zielinski, Nils Robbe, 2004: Past and Future of Airborne Pollution Control. Proceedings of the Interspill 2004 Conference, Trondheim, Norway, June 14-17, 2004.
- Minghelli-Roman, Audrey, S. Marni, F. Cauneau, L. Polidori, 2004: From hyperspectral satellite images to decision processus: a user-oriented approach. IGARSS 2004 Symposium "Science for Society Exploring and Managing a Changing Planet". IGARSS 2004, Anchorage, Alaska.
- Published abstract: “Drift forecast services at the Norwegian Meteorological Institute”, B. Hackett Proceedings of GODAE 2nd Symposium, St. Petersburg FL, USA, 1-3 November 2004.
- Nils Robbe, Theo Hengstermann, Oliver Zielinski, Barbara Cembella, 2005: Automated Analysis and Fusion of Multi-spectral Data in Airborne Oil Spill Remote Sensing. Proceedings of the Eighth International Conference on Remote Sensing for Marine and Coastal Environments, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada, May 17-19, 2005.
- Hamre, T., S. Sandven and É. Ó Tuama, “DISMAR: Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality”. Proceedings of 31st International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment, 20-24 June, 2005, St. Petersburg, Russia,
- Hackett, B., J. Albretsen, L.P. Røed, J.A. Johannessen and E. Svendsen, The MONCOZE Pilot Ocean Monitoring System (POMS); A Tool for Marine Environmental Monitoring, (submitted to Proceedings of 4th EuroGOOS Conference, 6-9 June 2005, Brest, France).
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- Shutler, J.D., Miller, P.I., Groom S.B. and Aiken J. Automatic near real-time mapping of MERIS data as input to a phytoplankton classifier, submitted to proceedings of the ESA MERIS-(A)TSR User’s Meeting 26-30 September 2005, 6pp.
- Hamre, T., S. Sandven and É. Ó Tuama, “DISMAR: Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality”. Submitted to proceedings of the ESA MERIS-(A)TSR User’s Meeting 26-30 September 2005, 6pp.

Presentations at conferences and workshops, other publications:

- Marine Institute 10th Anniversary Conference, Dublin: Attended by CMRC researchers: Eamonn O Tuama and Valerie Cummins. A brochure on DISMAR was prepared and distributed at the conference
- Security: Services and Benefits from GMES, Matera, Italy, January 2003: "Oil spill Automatic Detection from SAR Images" Speaker: Prof. Paolo Trivero, Università del Piemonte Orientale 'A.Avogadro'
- IGARSS'03, July 2003: Paper “Multiple classifier system based on attractor dynamics” was presented by Andrey Bogdanov (INI)
- CoastGIS'03, Genoa, Italy: Paper “A Web-based Distributed Architecture for Coastal Zone Management” was presented by Éamonn Ó Tuama (CMRC).
- GMES meeting, Baveno, Italy, November 2003: DISMAR poster presented by Stein Sandven (NERSC).
- Oceanology International 2004/Alliance for Marine Remote Sensing conference, Disaster Monitoring session, London, March 2004. Invited oral presentation by Steve Groom on Harmful Algal Blooms.
- OCEANIDES Workshop on Oil Spill Monitoring, Copenhagen, Denmark, May 2004: DISMAR project presented by T. Hamre (NERSC).
- Envisat Symposium, Salzburg, Austria, September 2004: Poster presentation: “DISMAR – Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality”. S. Sandven, NERSC
- Envisat Symposium, Salzburg, Austria, September 2004: Oral presentation: “Oil Spills Automatic Detection from SAR Images”. F. Nirchio, P. Trivero, W. Biamino, M. Sorgente et al. (ASI and UNIPMN).
- IGARSS 2004, Anchorage, Alaska, September 2004: Minghelli-Roman, Audrey, S. Marni, F. Cauneau, L. Polidori, 2004: From hyperspectral satellite images to decision processus: a user-

- oriented approach. IGARSS 2004 Symposium "Science for Society Exploring and Managing a Changing Planet".
- GODAE 2nd Symposium, St. Petersburg FL, USA, November 2004: Oral presentation: "Meeting the Marine Emergency Response Challenge", B. Hackett.
 - European expert group meeting in JRC, November 2004: DISPRO-1 was demonstrated to all 25 experts by F.Parthiot, Cedre.
 - IC EST 2005, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, January 2005: Braun N., M. Cysewski, G. Schymura, F. Ziemer; „Ship based radar mapping of sea surface features“; The International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology sponsored by the American Academy of Sciences January 23-26; 2005.
 - New Space Services for Maritime Users: The Impact of Satellite Technology on Maritime Legislation, Paris, February 2005: Poster entitled "DISMAR: Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality" presented and fact sheets handed out at the conference. Poster presentation by Francois Parthiot, Cedre.
 - Third Meeting of EGEMP (European Group of Experts on satellite Monitoring and assessment of sea-based oil Pollution), Ispra, Italy, April 2005: DISMAR was presented and DISPRO demonstrated by Francois Parthiot. CEDRE.
 - Remote Sensing and Bio-optical Modelling of the Baltic Sea, Gdansk, Poland, 2005. Miller, P., J. Shutler, and S. Groom, Oral presentation on Discrimination of harmful algal blooms using MODIS, MERIS and SAR, Miller, P., J. Shutler, and S. Groom (oral presentation)
 - Workshop on Remote sensing and Biooptical Modelling, Gedansk, Polen: DISMAR products and sensors developments were presented in "Use of ships of opportunity data for satellite validation." Kai Sørensen, Jo Høkedal, Eyvind Aas, NIVA.
 - The 20th German Hydrographers' Conference, Wilhemshaven, June 2005: M.Cysewski: "Radar scanning as method for detection of oil pollution and it's tracking"
 - 4th EuroGOOS conference in Brest, France, June 2005:
 - Presented poster: 'Ecosystem modelling in the context of a coastal observatory', K.Lewis¹, I.Allen¹, S. Groom¹, J. Siddorn², M. Holt². ¹Plymouth Marine Laboratory, Plymouth, UK. ²Met Office, Exeer, UK
 - Products and sensor developments from DISMAR was presented in the "The development of ships of opportunity monitoring system in Norwegian coastal waters." Kai Sørensen, J. Magnusson, J. Høkedal, T. Johnsen, D. Durand, J. Karud, G. Pedersen.
 - DISMAR was named in a poster on the Pilot Ocean Monitoring System (developed in Norway), which utilizes the technology developed for DISPRO. By B. Hackett, et al.
 - EARSeL Workshop on Remote Sensing of the Coastal Zone, Porto, June 2005: F.Ziemer: "Small scale sea surface current features observed by X-band radar"
 - 31st International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment, St. Petersburg, Russia, June 2005: T. Hamre¹, S. Sandven¹ and É. Ó. "DISMAR: Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality", by. ¹NERSC, ²CMRC. Oral presentation.
 - "Image and Signal Processing for Remote Sensing XI," part of the SPIE Remote Sensing Symposium, 2005, Bruges, Belgium, September 2005. A.V. Bogdanov, M. Toussaint, and S. Sandven, Recurrent modular network architecture for segmentation and classification of ERS SAR images.
 - 11th SPIE International Symposium on Remote Sensing; Bruges, Belgium, September 2005. Shutler J. D., Grant M. G. and Miller P. I., Towards spatial localisation of harmful algal blooms: statistics-based spatial anomaly detection (oral presentation)
 - MERIS-AATSR 2005 User Workshop, ESRIN, Frascati, Italy, September 2005:
 - T. Hamre¹, S. Sandven¹ and É. Ó Tuama²: "DISMAR: Data Integration System for Marine Pollution and Water Quality". ¹NERSC, ²CMRC Oral presentation.
 - Éamonn Ó Tuama. DISPRO - a portal for integrating EO products in a distributed GIS. Poster.
 - Shutler J., Miller P., Groom S., Aiken J., Automatic near-real time mapping of MERIS data as input to a phytoplankton classifier (oral presentation)
 - Sørensen, K., J. Karud, J. Høkedal and T. Johnsen: "An early warning algal bloom system combining remote sensing and in situ data is developed for coastal waters off Norway through the DISMAR project". Oral presentation.
 - Pettersson¹, L. H., A. Folkestad¹, E. Svendsen² and M. Skogen²: MERIS monitors algae blooms to early detect possible harmful blooms. ¹NERSC, ²Institute of Marine Research, Bergen. Oral presentation.

Appendix B. Consortium and contact persons

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